

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP PROJECT H2Mobility SPOKE 1– Deliverable **3.0.2**

SPOKE 1 – Aerospace and sustainable mobility
Flagship Project – H2Mobility

DELIVERABLE D3.0.2

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP PROJECT H2Mobility SPOKE 1– Deliverable **3.0.2**

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.

Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

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1. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

1.1 Objectives

The main objective of H2Mobility is to contribute to improve the technological readiness to the exploitation of H₂ as the renewable energy vector for the future mobility system. This goal will determine a strong demand for new technologies, new components, and innovative services for green H₂ storage (adsorbing and absorbing materials) and its subsequent distribution and use to provide energy on-demand (fuel cells, internal combustion engines). The activities include the **use of robust and established technology pathways to produce system to store** (e.g. adsorption and absorption in different matrices, chemical storage), **to distribute and to use** (fuel cells, internal combustion engines) **green hydrogen**. This implies innovation activities for the development of new solutions for components and subsystems in order to lower costs, fostering the market acceptance and supporting the creation of local supply chains.

Beside H₂ storage, distribution and use capabilities, the project will also address E-Fuels. In this regard, the research activity will focus mainly on the development of components, technologies and systems for conversion of CO₂ and other vectors into RFNBO (Renewable Fuels of Non-Biological Origin) in order to optimize bio-catalytic conversion, with the aim to exploit specific and optimized metabolic pathways. Additionally, the environmental benefits of producing and using RFNBO will be quantified according to LCA based methodology, as per the REDII and ICAO-CORSIA

1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per RM in the reporting period

1.2.1 Research Module 1

Research Module n. 1:	Start month: M1			End month: M36			
Title:	Hydrogen production						
Location in Mezzogiorno:	N						
RM Leader	POLITO						
Partners involved	Envipark	UNITO					
Type of action:	<i>Industrial Research</i>						
Effort in person/months:	POLITO: 1,85		Envipark: 2,95		UNITO: 0,226		
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Hydrogen production through electrical-based pathway: water electrolysis 2) Bio-based processes for H₂ production and aqueous phase reforming as alternative approaches of green H₂ production 						
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):							

1) Objective1/ Hydrogen production through electrical-based pathway: water electrolysis

Task 1.1 Technology briefs on Green Hydrogen generation by electrolysis (POLITO DENERG; ENVIPARK)

The technology briefs have been structured to address four key aspects of the technologies: status of technologies and processes, current market, current status and projections of performance and costs, potential and barriers. The technology briefs for alkaline and PEM electrolysis have been completed for what concerns the status of the technologies and processes and the current market. The analysis of the current status and projections of performance and costs is ongoing, together with the assessment of potential and barriers for alkaline and PEM technologies. Literature research is ongoing on the state-of-the-art of the electrolysis for low-temperature anion exchange membranes (AEM) electrolyzers, intermediate-temperature proton conducting electrolyzers and high-temperature solid oxide electrolyzers (SOEC). In the following lines, the main results are summarized.

Green Hydrogen production: state-of-the-art

Hydrogen can be produced starting from various primary energy sources and energy carriers and through different chemical or electro-chemical processes. Hydrogen production routes are identified with different colours to keep track of the input and production process from which hydrogen derives. “Black”, “grey” or “brown” refer to the production of hydrogen from coal, natural gas and lignite respectively. “Blue” is commonly used for the production of hydrogen from fossil fuels with CO₂ emissions reduced by the use of CCUS. Following the EU Hydrogen Strategy definition: “Green hydrogen is produced through the electrolysis of water (in an electrolyser, powered by electricity), and with the electricity stemming from renewable sources”. Other renewables-based paths to produce hydrogen currently exists, including thermal, thermo-chemical, photo, photo-chemical and biological routes. However, none of them has yet reached the commercial maturity and will not be solutions available on the near/medium term for the green hydrogen generation. Several types of electrolysis technologies exist: Alkaline and polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) electrolyzers are already commercial, whereas Solid Oxide Electrolyzers (SOE) are at the precommercial stage and anion exchange membranes (AEMs) and proton conducting electrolysis cells (PCEC) are at early stages of development.

Commercial low-temperature electrolyzers currently available (Alkaline and PEM) achieve a state-of-the art stack efficiency in the range 50%-70% (LHV calculated) and a system efficiency in the range of 50-80 kWh/kgH₂ (electrical). Targets for these technologies are to increase stack efficiency over 75% and to reach a system efficiency below 45 kWh/kgH₂. The high-temperature electrolysis systems (SOE) already achieve very high performance, up to 85% of stack efficiency and 40 kWh/ kgH₂ system efficiency [2]. The research and development for the high-temperature electrolysis is more focused on increasing the durability and reduce the capital cost of the stack production.

The cost of green hydrogen depends largely on the cost of renewable electricity needed to power the electrolyser unit, which is the main cost component of green hydrogen. A low cost of electricity is therefore a necessary condition for a competitive green hydrogen. However, a low electricity cost is not enough by itself for competitive green hydrogen production, as reductions in the capital cost of electrolyser are also needed. This is the second largest cost component of green hydrogen. The cost of green hydrogen production is reported to range between 2.5-6 \$/kg, with a range of 1.5-3 \$/kg for the hydrogen from steam methane reforming production [1]. Green hydrogen is already close to being competitive with blue hydrogen today in regions where the price of renewable electricity is very low, but these are usually far from demand centres. In most location, green hydrogen cost is 2-3 times higher compared to blue hydrogen. According to IRENA, a combination of cost reductions in electricity and electrolyzers, combined with increased efficiency and operating lifetime, can deliver 80% reduction in hydrogen cost compared to the present levels. If a rapid scale-up of electrolyzers production takes place, green hydrogen is expected to start becoming competitive with blue hydrogen by 2030 in countries where electricity prices are of 30 \$/MWh, and cheaper than any alternative (ie. < 1 \$/kg) by 2040 [2].

Electrolysers are typically divided into four main technologies: alkaline electrolyzers (AEL), polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) electrolyzers, Solid Oxide Electrolysers (SOE) and anion exchange membrane (AEM) electrolyzers. These are distinguished based on electrolyte type and temperature of operation, from which the materials of the different components of the electrolyzer depend. The principles of operation of the different types of electrolysis cells are depicted in Figure 1.1. In the case of Solid Oxide Electrolysers, electrolyte typically are oxygen ions conductors; in the case that protons are the mobile ions in the electrolyte, then they are defined as Proton Conducting Electrolysers (PCEC).

In the alkaline electrolyzers, the electrolyte transports OH anions in a liquid solution (typically KOH). The electrodes and produced gases are physically separated by a porous inorganic diaphragm (also called a separator) that is permeable to the electrolyte solution. In PEM, AEM, and solid oxide electrolyzers, the electrodes are separated by an electron-insulating solid electrolyte, which is transporting ions and at the same time acts as physical separator for the produced gases (hydrogen and oxygen).

Alkaline electrolyzers

AEL represents the most mature between the electrolysis technologies. The diaphragm (separator) in the cells is a polymeric membrane, usually Zirfon® Pearl, a porous material made by 85% zirconium oxide (ZrO₂) and 15% of polysulfone (PSU) [4]. To prevent the intermixing of oxygen and hydrogen produced at the electrodes, the diaphragm is thick (around 0.25 mm) and spacers are sometimes included by some manufacturers between electrodes and diaphragms to further avoid the intermixing of gases. The electrolyte is an aqueous solution of 25-30 % wt. KOH, in which the ionic charge carrier is the hydroxyl ion OH⁻, with KOH and water permeating

through the porous structure of the diaphragm. For both electrodes, usually nickel (Ni) coated stainless-steel materials are exploited, because of the low cost and good performance [1,5,6].

AEL have a simple stack and system design and are relatively easy to manufacture. Currently, they have electrode areas as high as 3 square metres (m²) but can achieve only limited current density levels (0.2 – 0.8 A/cm²) due to the thick diaphragms and added spacers that result into high ohmic resistances across the two electrodes [2]. The stack pressure reaches up to 30 bar in current AEL plants and the operating temperature is in the range 70-90°C.

The typical BoP of an AEL is depicted in Figure 1.2. AELs require to have a circulating liquid electrolyte solution. This creates a pressure drop that requires pumping peripherals to move the electrolyte solution through the stack. After leaving the stack, the electrolyte solution is separated from the gases produced in gas-liquid separators placed above the stack and it is recirculated back to the stack. In the separators, the water phase is removed at the bottom and the gas phase at the top.

Figure 1.2 – Typical Balance of Plant of AEL system [2]

The water management system regulates the filling level of the gas-liquid separators. The hydrogen obtained from the gas-liquid separator undergoes a series of further steps of separation of residual liquid, oxygen traces removal and drying to reach high purity levels (>99.9%). Final steps of compression can be included in the plant depending on the final pressure required. Oxygen is a by-product of the AEL electrolysis, but it is obtained at the top of separators with a level of purity similar to that of the hydrogen and can be easily treated to obtain a valuable high-purity product.

PEM electrolyzers

PEM cells are mainly composed by the Membrane Electrode assemble (MEA), in which electrochemical reactions takes place. The MEA is basically a sandwiched structure containing a thin (0.2 mm) polymer membrane (perfluorosulfonic acid (PFSA) membrane - usually Nafion®) and the two electrodes. Bipolar plates act as separators between the series-connected cells, guarantying both electrical conductivity and physical strength to the stack. The plates are hollowed, in order to enable the flows of the water inside the MEA and the evacuation of the gases.

The membrane is chemically and mechanically robust, which allows the operation at relevant levels of differential pressure between the electrodes. This is a great advantage, as allows the electrolyzer to produce hydrogen at high pressure, while feeding the water at low pressure. PEM cells can operate at a pressure up to 70 bar with the oxygen side at atmospheric pressure. The acidic environment provided by the membrane, high voltages, and oxygen evolution in the anode creates a harsh oxidative environment, demanding the use of materials that can withstand these conditions. Titanium-based materials, noble metal catalysts and protective coatings are necessary, not only to provide long-term stability to cell components, but also to provide optimal electron conductivity and cell efficiency. Platinum-group metals are usually employed as catalysts for the electrodes. Typical anode iridium loading is 2 mg/cm², while cathode platinum loadings range between 0.2 and 0.5 mg/cm² [7-8].

Electrode areas are approaching 2000 cm² and the current density is in the range 1-2 A/cm² and the cells usually operate in the temperature range 50-80 °C. PEMs have a compact and simple system design. In Figure 1.3, a typical BoP is shown. PEM typically require the use of circulation pumps for water, heat exchangers to maintain a fixed temperature at the cell inlet, pressure control and monitoring at the anode (oxygen) side. At the cathode side, a gas-separator, a de-oxygenation component to remove remnant oxygen and gas dryer are required. Hydrogen is obtained with a high purity level (> 99.9%). For PEM electrolyzers also, oxygen is a high-purity by-product.

Figure 1.3 – Typical Balance of Plant of PEM electrolysis system [2]

Concerning the pressure, PEM systems are implemented in different possible configurations: atmospheric, differential, and balanced pressure. Under a balanced pressure operation, the anode and cathode are designed to run under the same pressure level. The PEM membrane electrolyte allows for operation under differential pressure, typically 30 bar to 70 bar. This configuration requires a thicker membrane to improve the mechanical stability and decreases gas permeation, which reduces efficiency. Depending on the pressure of the final application a hydrogen compressor can be also included in the BoP.

Electrolyzers market

The global electrolysis capacity installed worldwide (MW values), divided by regions, is shown in Figure 1.4 for the period 2015-2020. Around 40% of the global installed capacity is located Europe, which will remain the dominant region due to the strong policy support coming from numerous hydrogen strategies adopted in the last years and the prominence of electrolytic hydrogen in the Covid-19 recovery packages of countries such as Germany, France and Spain. Figure 1.4 shows the global installed electrolysis capacity by technology, for the same period. Electrolysers have reached enough maturity to scale up manufacturing and deployment to significantly reduce costs, which is reflected in three consecutive years of record capacity deployment in 2018, 2019 and 2020. Close to 70 MW of electrolysis became operational in 2020, bringing total installed capacity to almost 300 MW.

Figure 4 – Global installed electrolysis capacity by region [MW] and by technology. Re-elaboration from [11] and [12]

Alkaline electrolysers, today the most mature electrolysis technology, have traditionally dominated the market because they have been widely deployed in the chlor-alkali industry and are the most installed technology covering more than half the electrolyzers market (> 160 MW). For the dedicated production of hydrogen, however, many new projects are now opting for PEM designs, and their deployment in the past three years has even surpassed that of alkaline electrolysers. In 2020 the world's second and third largest electrolyser projects became operational (the largest project is the 25-MW Industrial Cachimayo plant in Peru). In March, a 10-MW single-stack alkaline electrolyser entered into operations in Japan (powered by solar PV), and in December a 20-MW multi-stack PEM electrolyser in Canada (powered by hydropower) finished testing and started operating in January 2021. In addition, there were significantly more announcements for projects in the order of hundreds of megawatts in 2020, some of which have reached the final investment decision phase and are expected to begin operating in the early 2020s. It is still unclear which between the alkaline and PEM designs will dominate the market as the technology scales up. Although alkaline technology has the advantages of maturity and lower cost, the price of PEM electrolysers is also falling rapidly, and they have a smaller footprint and can deliver hydrogen at high pressure (30-60 bar, compared with 1-30 bar for alkaline). In addition, PEM electrolysers could benefit for spillover technological learning benefits from the development of PEM fuel cells.

SOE are being installed only in few demonstration projects. All these projects are in Europe and focus mostly on producing synthetic hydrocarbons, which is an interesting niche market for SOECs.

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Task 1.2 Technology development – modeling electrolysis system at SRU/stack level (POLITO DENERG)

In order to develop a model platform for electrolysers at SRU/stack level, an initial step is the development of a model at cell level. The thermo-electrochemical modeling platform for single cells for intermediate and high-temperature electrolysers with solid oxide electrolyte has been developed. The model has been developed using finite elements software (COMSOL Multiphysics) and it is developed up to the boundary with interconnect plates. The model calibration and validation is ongoing using literature data. The model platform is described in the following lines.

T1.2.1 Cell platform model

The model takes in account the governing equations of mass and momentum transport, charge, and species conservation, and energy transfer.

- **Charge balance**

A cell includes materials with electric conduction, ionic conduction, or both, in the case of the electrodes. The transport of these charges is described by the Ohm's law equation, expressed as:

$$-\nabla \cdot (\sigma_i \nabla V_i) = S_{i,a,c}$$

where σ_i represent the ionic or electronic conductivity. V_i is the electric potential, and S_i is the charge source term due to electrochemical reactions. This equation can be applied both the electrodes and the electrolyte. The ionic conductivity of the active part of the electrodes can be calculated using the following equation:

$$\sigma_{GDE} = \sigma_{elect} f_i$$

Where σ_{elect} is the conductivity of the electrolyte, f_i is a correction factor, which takes into account the volume of ionic conductor inside the active volume of the electrode (Gas Diffusion Electrode - GDE). The parameter S_i is defined by the equation:

$$S_{i,a/c} = \pm A_{TPB} j_{a,c}$$

Where A_{TPB} is the specific surface area of the Three Phase Boundary (TPB), which can be considered uniformly distributed in the GDE layer of the electrodes.

- **Mass balance**

Transportation phenomena are mainly driven by diffusion and convection in the porous electrodes of the cell and in the gas channel equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho\omega_i) + \nabla \cdot (\rho\omega_i \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i + R_i$$

where, considering the mixture of N species (with i that goes from 1 to N), ρ is the density, \mathbf{u} the mass average velocity vector, ω_i the mass fraction, \mathbf{J}_i the diffusion flux, and R_i the rate of consumption or production of a species i [1]. The diffusion flux of chemical species \mathbf{J}_i is written as follows:

$$\mathbf{J}_i = -\rho\omega_i \sum_k D_{i,k,eff} (\nabla x_k + \frac{1}{p} [(x_k - \omega_k) \nabla p])$$

Where $D_{i,k,eff}$ is the effective diffusivity and x_k is the molar fraction of the k -th species [1]. Assuming the porous electrode to be composed by a solid phase made of spheres and the bed phase surrounding the spheres treated as the void fraction of the electrode, the Buggerman's equation can be used for the calculation of the effective diffusivity:

$$D_{i,k,eff} = \varepsilon^{1.5} D_{ik}$$

Where ε represents the porosity of the electrodes.

- **Heat balance**

Temperature is a fundamental parameter, due to the dependence of different parameters to its value. In the case of intermediate and high-temperature cells, radiative heat transfer is usually neglected in the literature. So, the only heat transfer phenomena included in the model are convection and conduction. Conductive heat transfer can be expressed as:

$$\rho C_{p,eff} u \nabla T = \nabla \cdot (k_{eff} \nabla T) + Q_{gen}$$

Where ρ is the density, c_p the specific heat capacity and k_{eff} the effective conductivity. This equation is applied to all the domains, (solid, gas and porous), so they depend on the domain considered. For porous materials, these three parameters are weighted for the solid and fluid component, obtaining effective parameters. Q_{gen} is the heat source term, that varies depending on the part of the cell considered. The thermal conductivity term can be written as follow:

$$k_{eff} = \varepsilon_p k_f + (1 - \varepsilon_p) k_s$$

Where k_f and k_s represent the thermal conductivity of the gas and solid phase, respectively, and ε_p is the porosity. Convection heat transfer is related to the flow of the species and can be expressed as follows:

$$(\rho C_p)_f \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (k_f \nabla T_f) - (\rho C_p)_f u \nabla T_f$$

Where T_f is the temperature of the fluid, k_f its thermal conductivity, and u the velocity field vector. The heat sources are due to the electrochemical reaction irreversibility and to the Joule's effect in electrodes and electrolyte.

$$Q_{chem} = -\Delta S_e \frac{T \cdot J \cdot a_v}{n_e F}$$

$$Q_{ohm} = \frac{J^2}{\sigma}$$

Where, in the second equation, the σ is the electrolyte ionic conductivity or electrode electronic conductivity, depending by the case, while in the first equation, ΔS_e is the change in entropy of the reaction [2]. Heat sources are not considered in the gas channel, unless a reactive mixture is fed to the electrodes.

- *Electrochemical reactions*

The charge transfer kinetics can be modeled by the Butler-Volmer equation, that here is reported for the anode and for the cathode:

$$i_a = i_{0,a} \left[\exp\left(\frac{\alpha_{b,a} F \eta_{act,a}}{RT}\right) - \exp\left(\frac{-\alpha_{f,a} F \eta_{act,a}}{RT}\right) \right]$$

$$i_c = i_{0,c} \left[\exp\left(\frac{\alpha_{b,c} F \eta_{act,c}}{RT}\right) - \exp\left(\frac{-\alpha_{f,c} F \eta_{act,c}}{RT}\right) \right]$$

Where $i_{0,a}$ and $i_{0,c}$ are the exchange current densities for anode and cathode respectively, alphas are the backward and forward transfer coefficients [3]. The exchange current densities can be calculated as:

$$i_{0,a} = i_{0,a,ref} \prod_{i:v_i>0} \frac{p_i^{\frac{\alpha_c v_i}{n}}}{p_{i,ref}} \prod_{i:v_i<0} \frac{p_i^{-\frac{\alpha_a v_i}{n}}}{p_{i,ref}}$$

$$i_{0,c} = i_{0,c,ref} \prod_{i:v_i>0} \frac{p_i^{\frac{\alpha_c v_i}{n}}}{p_{i,ref}} \prod_{i:v_i<0} \frac{p_i^{-\frac{\alpha_a v_i}{n}}}{p_{i,ref}}$$

Where $i_{0,a,ref}$ and $i_{0,c,ref}$ are the references value for anode and cathode respectively.

- *Model application*

The model has been applied to the simulation of a 2D rectangular anode-supported Proton Conductive Cell (PCC), as detailed in [3], featuring an area equivalent to that of a circular geometry with a 3 cm radius. The materials considered are BCZY for the electrolyte, NiO-BCZY as fuel electrode, and BCZY-BGLC for the air electrode. The geometry includes: fuel flow channel, fuel electrode gas diffusion electrode layer (GDL), active volume of the fuel electrode (GDE), membrane, active volume of air electrode (GDE), air electrode gas diffusion electrode layer (GDL), and air flow channel. The flow channels represent the channels of the interconnector. The electrodes were divided into two volumes: a gas diffusion layer, where the reaction doesn't take place, and an active volume, where reaction takes place. Geometry parameters were taken from [3] and are here reported in the following table.

Table 1. Geometry parameters of 2D cell model

Length	6cm
Air and fuel flow channels thickness	500 μ m
Fuel GDL thickness	20 μ m
Fuel GDE thickness	20 μ m
Electrolyte thickness	10 μ m
Air GDE thickness	20 μ m
Air GDL thickness	330 μ m

For this simulation, the ion conductivity of the electrolyte was considered fixed, and equal to $1.4 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ S/cm}$ [4][5]. The correction factor f_i has been considered equal to 0.2 [3]. For what concern the electronic conductivity of the electrodes, it has been assumed equal to 10^5 S/m [3]. The specific surface area of the TPB assumed is 10^9 1/m . The porosity of the electrodes has been set as 0.4 [3][4]. The references values of $i_{0,a,ref}$ and $i_{0,c,ref}$ assumed are 1 A/cm^2 .

The cell has been simulated to operate in electrolysis mode, feeding steam (with oxygen traces) at the anode with a molar fraction of water vapor of 0.97, assuming steam recirculation with oxygen separation (i.e. not complete separation as it is not necessary) on the anodic side. Hydrogen is recirculated at the cathode, considering it slightly humidified, with a molar fraction of water vapor of 0.1. The operating temperature considered for the simulation is 600°C , imposing it as inlet temperature of the fluids. For what concern the potential of the cell, ground potential is fixed to the anode, and the cell voltage is imposed at the cathode, starting with a value of 0.98 V (OCV). For the calculation of i-V polarization curve and power density curve, the V_{cell} was varied within a range of 0.98V to 1.2V. No flux condition was imposed for all the boundaries of the cell, except for inlet and outlet section, where a mass flow rate and atmospheric pressure were imposed respectively. Considering the thermal model, thermal symmetry was applied to the upper and lower boundary, while a thermal insulation was applied for the side boundaries of the cell.

Figure 1.5 displays the i-V polarization curve obtained from the simulation. The Open Circuit Voltage (OCV) value is 0.98 V, with subsequent current densities showing negative values. This outcome can be attributed to the specific electrolysis mode chosen. In Figure 1.62, power density vs current density graph is reported. The peak of power density of 3.25 W/cm^2 is obtained for a current density of 2 A/cm^2 .

Figure 1.7 illustrates the trend of temperature within the cell, representing the curves of average, maximum, and minimum temperature as a function of current density. At a voltage of 1.282V, the condition of thermoneutrality – in which the heat generation by irreversibility is balanced by the heat absorbed by the reaction – is reached, and the temperature inside the cell becomes uniform and equal to 600°C as at OCV.

Figure 1.5. Cell polarization

Figure 1.6. Cell power density

Figure 1.7 Maximum, minimum and average cell temperature.

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Task 1.3 Technology testing – Test procedures/protocols for electrolyzers and components (POLITO DENERG; ENVIPARK)

The activity that has been performed in this task is the review of standardized protocols and testing infrastructures for testing Alkaline Membrane electrolyzers. The summary of the results is provided in the following lines.

Task 1.3.1 review of test protocols for AEM

A review of the main international test protocols for AEM electrolyzers has been performed. The summary of the results is reported.

- ***EU: Harmonized protocols for testing of low temperature water electrolyzers***

Assessing the performance and the durability of electrochemical devices (i.e., electrolyser) according to commonly agreed protocols and performing tests under conditions that are representative of current and future applications is an acknowledged need for both industry and research. The “*EU harmonized protocols for testing of low temperature water electrolyzers*” is a technical report published by JRC in 2021 that specifically aims at addressing these requirements.

- European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Tsotridis, G., Pilenga, A., EU harmonized protocols for testing of low temperature water electrolysis, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/58880>

Harmonized protocols and methodology allow to improve the repeatability and reproducibility of the test results enhancing their comparability. Moreover, they can boost the representativity of the experimental campaigns in simulating the real-world conditions and applications. Finally, the testing protocols identify specific Key Performance Indices (KPIs) that can be fundamental to assess performance and durability.

The report consists of a set of operating conditions, testing protocols and procedure to be applied in order to assess both the performance and the durability of low temperature electrolyzers. The document considers three different technologies of low temperature water electrolyzers, including Anion exchange membrane (AEM). According to the testing protocols, performance and durability of single cell and short stack can be assessed by performing in-situ tests over a wide range of operating conditions and measuring the electrochemical properties (i.e., voltage and current). The in-situ testing activity at cell and stack level enable the evaluation of the performance by using a set of indicators that can be derived either as direct experimental results or post-processing the test outcomes.

Most frequently used in-situ tests are:

- Polarization curve (I-V curve) for evaluating the overall electrochemical performances
- Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) for identifying the contribution of ohmic, activation and concentration losses and evaluating the reaction rates, the diffusion coefficients and the charge transfer resistance

- Cyclic voltammetry (CV) for measuring the reaction kinetics and determining the electrochemical active surface area.

detailed methodologies to correctly perform the in-situ tests are described in three specific reports published by JRC in 2018:

- T. Malkow, A. Pilenga, G. Tsotridis, and G. De Marco, EU harmonised polarization curve test method for low-temperature water electrolysis, EUR 29182 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2018, ISBN 978-92-79-81992-6, doi:10.2760/324006, JRC104045.
- T. Malkow, A. Pilenga, G. Tsotridis, EU harmonised test procedure: electrochemical impedance spectroscopy for water electrolysis cells, EUR 29267 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2018, ISBN 978-92-79-88739-0, doi:10.2760/8984, JRC107053
- T. Malkow, G. De Marco, G. Tsotridis, EU harmonised cyclic voltammetry test method for low temperature water electrolysis single cells, EUR 29285 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2018, ISBN 978-92-79-89871-6, doi:10.2760/140687, JRC111151

order to carry out the in-situ experimental campaign, the JRC protocol specifies the reference setting value of the different test input parameters (e.g., cell/stack temperature, electrolyte inlet concentration for ALK electrolyser, hydrogen and oxygen outlet pressure). The protocol also identifies a set of test output parameters (e.g., electrolyte outlet concentration for ALK electrolyser, hydrogen and oxygen production rate and quality) to be measured while performing the tests. The operating conditions identified as a reference in the protocols should theoretically represent the centre of the normal operating range. However, in some cases, the electrolysers can be forced to work under operating conditions that are outside of this window.

- **DOE-NREL**

The HydroGEN consortium is led by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory and includes Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Sandia National Laboratories, Idaho National Laboratory, and Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory. HydroGEN is funded by DOE's Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Technologies Office in the Office of Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy. The consortium organizes the "Annual Advanced Water Splitting Technology Pathways Benchmarking and Protocols Workshop" in which member from the industry, the national laboratories and the academia review protocols for testing and benchmarking specific materials and components. These protocols are not yet harmonized and standardized, but they are posted on the Energy Materials Network Website and published on open access peer-reviewed journals.

- **NIST**

The only testing protocol for electrolysers by NIST was published by B. McCollum et al. in 1927.

- **ISO TC 197**

The Working Group 34 is responsible for the standardization of "Hydrogen generators using water electrolysis test protocols and safety requirements". In 2019, the ISO/TC 197 published the "ISO 22734:2019 Hydrogen generators using water electrolysis — Industrial, commercial, and residential applications". This document "defines the construction, safety and performance requirements of modular and factory-matched hydrogen gas generation appliances, herein referred to hydrogen generators, using electrochemical reactions to electrolyte water to produce hydrogen". The standards defined in this document can be applied to different electrolysers, including the following ion transport medium typology: solid polymeric materials with basic function group additions, such as anion exchange membrane (AEM). This document is applicable to electrolysers intended for industrial and commercial uses and indoor and outdoor residential application.

The ISO 22734-2019 defines the standards requirements for: the operating conditions; the risk management; the mechanical equipment; the electrical equipment, wiring and ventilation; the control system; the ion transport medium; and the protection of service personnel.

The ISO 22734-2019 identifies the tests that have to be performed in order to verify that an electrolyser is compliant with the design specification. According to the standard, the following tests have to be conducted: electrical, pressure, leakage, dilution, protection against the spread of fire, temperature, environmental, performance, spillage, overflow and drain, mechanical strength, stability, vent and sound level. The standard specifies the basic test arrangement and the reference test conditions to be adopted while performing the testing activity. More in detail, the test should be performed at the factory or at the installation site (if applicable) and while conducting the test the electrolyser system (i.e., stack and BoP with air filters, start-up devices, venting or exhaust systems) has to be installed in accordance with the manufacturer's instruction to replicate the manner in which it has to be installed and operated.

Currently, the ISO/TC 197 is developing two standards focused on the testing protocols and guidance:

- ISO/AWI 22734-1 Hydrogen generators using water electrolysis — Industrial, commercial, and residential applications — Part 1: General requirements, test protocols and safety requirements
- ISO/AWI TR 22734-2 Hydrogen generators using water electrolysis — Part 2: Testing guidance for performing electricity grid service

Task 1.4 Evaluation of r-SOC (reversible Fuel cell) installation in residential and commercial eco-building: permitting procedures, safety aspects for the installation. (POLITO-DENERG)

As a result of the adoption of the MIMIT decree 7/7/2023 that updated the technical regulations on safety in the design, construction, and operation of H₂ electrolysis production and storage facilities, an in-depth analysis was carried out on the specific impact of this regulation on reversible SOEFC systems, updating the outcomes of REFLEX project over this topic.

2) Objective2/ Bio-based processes for H₂ production and aqueous phase reforming as alternative approaches of green H₂ production

Task 1.5 BIO-Electrochemical processes for H₂ production (POLITO DISAT)

During the second semester of the first year of the project we focused on the anodic side of the microbial bio-electrochemical cells. Microbial Electrolysis Cells (MECs) share the same technology for their anode of Microbial Fuel Cells (MFCs) and in both the systems, the anode electrode plays a crucial role in improving the overall devices' performance. At the anode an electroactive biofilm must develop, whose electrochemical activity plays a key role in defining performances of both the two classes of devices. Electroactive biofilms are indeed able to directly convert the chemical energy trapped in organic matter (i.e., the fuel) into electrical energy, thus acting as the bio-catalyst for the oxidation reaction. To reach this purpose the electrode's surface properties as hydrophilicity, porosity and electrical conductivity have a great importance to design robust and reliable systems.

In MFCs the anode is coupled with a cathode mimicking the one of traditional fuel cells, thus useful to directly extract electrical power as the output. In MECs the power produced at the anode is directly used to perform water electrolysis. To optimize bio-electrochemical H₂ production the optimization of bio-anodes is thus mandatory.

During this reporting period we started two sets of experiments in the labs.

With the first set we started the of brush-shaped carbon-based electrodes (shown in **Figure 1.8a**) to increase the surface area available for biofilm formation and thus the output energy of the system. The complete devices are shown in **Figure 1.8b**): they have bottle-shape that recall the structure of the H-cell selected for MECs, as already reported in the previous progress report.

Figure 1 a) brush-shaped carbon-based electrode; b) bottle-shape cell under investigation in the first set of experiments; c) carbon-based planer electrode; d) single chamber MFC used for the second set of experiments

The second set explores the decoration of conventional planar carbon-based electrodes shown in **Figure 1.8c**) with highly conductive polymer to promote the biofilm adhesion. The cell used in this experiment is a single chamber MFC as proposed in **Figure 1.8d**).

Task 1.6 Aqueous phase reforming (POLITO DISAT)

In the second semester, the work was focused on the technical, economic and environmental feasibility of obtaining SAFs (Sustainable Aviation Fuel) by hydrogenation of vegetable oils thanks to in-situ hydrogen production via aqueous phase reforming (APR) of the by-produced glycerol. The novel implementation of APR would avoid the environmental burden of conventional fossil-derived hydrogen production, as well as intermittency and storage issues related to the use of RES-based (renewable energy sources) electrolysers. The conceptual design of a conventional and advanced (APR-aided) biorefinery was performed, considering a standard plant capacity equal to 180 ktonne/y of palm oil. For the advanced scenario, the feed underwent hydrolysis into glycerol and fatty acids; hence, the former was subjected to APR to provide hydrogen, which was further used in the hydrotreatment reactor where the fatty acids were deoxygenated. The techno-economic results showed that APR implementation led to a slight increase of the fixed capital investment by 6.6% compared to the conventional one, while direct manufacturing costs decreased by 22%. In order to get a 10% internal rate of return, the minimum fuel selling price was found equal to 1.84\$/kg, which is 17% lower than the one derived from conventional configurations (2.20 \$/kg). The life-cycle GHG emission assessment showed that the carbon footprint of the advanced scenario was equal to ca. 12g CO₂/MJ(SAF), i.e., 54% lower than the conventional one (considering an energy-based allocation). The sensitivity analysis pointed out that the cost of the feedstock, SAF yield and the chosen plant size are key parameters for the marketability of this biorefinery, while the energy price has a negligible impact; moreover, the source of hydrogen has significant consequences on the environmental footprint of the plant.

Task 1.7 Materials for Hydrogen production (UNITO, POLITO DISAT Team).

POLITO DISAT

The catalyst used for the APR reaction remains a 5% Pt/C, provided by a commercial supplier in powder form, of which 80% had a size <106µm. The catalyst was used as received. In some tests the alternative Pt/Al₂O₃ samples were prepared by impregnation in DISAT lab and also tested, for the sake of comparison.

Characterization of both samples has been carried out on terms of surface area reduction and/or carbon deposition with aging.

UNITO

Hydrogen produced by bio-based processes is usually contaminated by other gases. In the second semester, activities on hydride-forming alloys have been carried out. In fact, the use of hydrides is suitable for simultaneous purification and storage of contaminated hydrogen feed streams, being able to supply high-purity hydrogen to fuel cells. Hydrogen purity enhances cell lifetime and efficiency, while degradation arises from

hydrogen mixtures featuring detrimental species, the most studied being CO, CO₂, CH₄, NH₃ and H₂S. It is important to discriminate between deactivation, which is the reversible passivation towards hydrogen, and poisoning, or irreversible passivation.

Hydrogen purification based on metal hydrides is under active development since 1970s. As-synthesized intermetallic alloys are not able to absorb hydrogen because they exhibit low specific surface areas, and they are passivated by an oxide layer when exposed to air. To cope with these issues, alloys are grinded to fine powders and then activated by performing successive absorption and desorption cycles in pure hydrogen. This way, hydrogen reduces and breaks the oxide layer. Absorption and desorption of hydrogen are operated in continuous-flow mode by acting on temperature and pressure. It is necessary to cool down the system during absorption because the hydrogenation reaction is exothermic, whereas hydrogen desorption needs heating. Industrial or domestic waste hot water is useful to decrease the environmental footprint and the energy consumption of the process. Metal hydride phase forms when the system is brought to the equilibrium temperature and pressure of the alloy, while impurities and contaminants keep flowing out. If not drained by a purge gas, they accumulate inside the reactor and reduce the hydrogen pressure, hindering absorption. Since draining inevitably purges hydrogen together with impurities, it is convenient to reach a tradeoff between the quantity of gas drained (off-gas) and the absorption performance.

Getters are a heterogeneous family of materials able to chemisorb gaseous compounds in solid state, especially hydrogen and its isotopes. Hydride-forming getters are intermetallic alloys referred to as non-evaporable getters (NEG), and they are the most diffused nowadays. Among NEG, the main compound types are Zr and Ti-based getters. Both types are characterized by high storage capacity, fast kinetics, easy activation, and extremely low hydrogen equilibrium pressure at room temperature.

In the second semester, UNITO activities focused on the characterization of ST707 and ZAO1 getter compounds, manufactured and supplied by SAES Getters. Since their use in hydrogen purification is a research topic under active development, the main objective of the work was to characterize their microstructure and assess their cycling performance in pure hydrogen. The microstructure and hydriding performance of ST707 and ZAO1 were studied with SEM, PXRD and DSC techniques, and with Sieverts method. Concerning the characterization of as received samples, SEM-EDX analysis showed that both samples are characterized by eutectic microstructure, and elemental compositions of areas observed in BSE images are in good agreement with literature. Furthermore, according to PXRD results, both materials consist of an hcp phase and a C15 Laves phase. Hydrogenation experiments showed a poorer hydriding performance for ZAO1 with respect to ST707. ZAO1 absorbed 0.66 wt.% of hydrogen after 12 minutes, against the 0.97 wt.% absorbed by ST707.

In addition, a poorer dehydriding performance was observed for ZAO1 with respect to ST707 during DSC experiment. In fact, hydrided phases in ZAO1 require a lower equilibrium pressure to desorb with respect to those in ST707. The difference in dehydriding temperatures is also important, since hydrided phases in ZAO1 start desorbing at higher temperatures. After DSC measurement, both samples were only partially dehydrided. Considering the above results, as received getters are not suitable for reversible hydrogen storage, since they require high temperatures and very low equilibrium pressures to desorb. It would be useful to understand if its elemental composition can be tailored to allow for desorption at higher equilibrium pressures.

Obtained results will hopefully be useful for future research on purification of contaminated bio-hydrogen streams. For applications, it is crucial to assess the cycling stability of getter compounds in contaminated hydrogen, and especially bio-hydrogen produced from renewable sources.

Output and results:

The overall activities that have been performed in this reporting period are the following

- The analysis of bio-precursors for H₂ production has been extended to other impacting categories
- Analysis of existing regulations has been carried out
- Validation and calibration of models have been carried out
- Experimental activity started for H₂ production through different approaches

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

No equipment

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

For the next reporting period we expect to get the first set of results for the experiments related to H₂ production via bio-electrolysers.

Future tests will aim to change the catalyst composition in the application of ethanol APR.

1.2.2 Research Module 2

Research Module n. 2:	Start month: M1	End month: M36
Title: Hydrogen storage		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	UNITO	
Partners involved	POLITO	
Type of action:	<i>Industrial Research</i>	
Effort in person/months:	UNITO:0,226	POLITO:0,64
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):		
<p>Innovative solutions will be developed to produce hybrid materials for the chemical storage of hydrogen. This ambitious goal will be achieved by combining species with a high gravimetric hydrogen content such as ammonia borane or with organic aromatic compounds containing heteroatoms such as nitrogen. Within the project, stable materials with up to one hundred release/regeneration cycles with high hydrogen release capacity will be produced. A technical solution will then be implemented that will couple the materials for storage with a controlled release system by means of thermal stimulation based on their confinement in heat exchanger-based systems.</p>		
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):		
Task 2.1 Aminoborane materials for hydrogen storage (POLITO DISAT)		
<p>During the second semester of the first year, the activities relate to the task 2.1 had been mainly focused on the solid-state reactivity of amino borane through its incorporation into polymer elevate porosity and functionalization. Firstly, composites containing amino borane and sulphonated poly ellagic acids were prepared with different concentration of hydrogen carrier and studied using thermochemical approach in order to evaluate thermodynamic parameters together with the hydrogen release. Additionally, multilayers composites containing nanocrystalline cellulose and amino borane with a thin layer of palladium were also prepared and tested. Both activities have been resulting with the preparation of manuscripts. Nevertheless, the hydrolysis of amino borane in water was also studied using a waste derive iron tailored catalyst. This activity was run by modifying a pig manure with ferrite allowing to reach catalytic performances comparable with noble metal-based materials. The results were published on the International Journal of Hydrogen Science ("Hydrogen evolution through ammonia borane hydrolysis over iron tailored pig manure catalyst", Gianola et al., accepted manuscript).</p>		
Task 2.2 Aromatic heteroatom compounds materials for hydrogen storage (POLITO DISAT)		
<p>During the second semester of the first year, the activity relates to the task 2.2 had been mainly focused on the synthesis of phenyl derivatives of amino borane and mix of amino borane with aromatic amines. These activities have been focused on the entrapping of low boiling point compounds produced during the thermal degradative processes of amino borane. Particularly, the in-situ formation of heteroaromatic compounds showed a beneficial effect reducing the loss of volatile boron-based materials. Actually, a first article is in preparation and a campaign of measurements of new heteroaromatic/inorganic hybrid systems is running.</p>		

For the next report, we will discuss the advancement in this specific topic targeting a full modulable reactivity in solid state of chemical hydrogen carriers.

Task 2.3 Development and integration of storage systems based on metal hydrides in mobility systems (UNITO)

The use of hydrogen as energy vector implies the development of the necessary infrastructures for hydrogen handling. In particular, the use of compressed hydrogen is crucial in mobility systems. A two-stage metal hydride compressor was developed and integrated in a small-scale hydrogen refuelling station at prototype level. In the second semester, the compression on site of green hydrogen using metal hydrides was investigated, taking into account all the necessary aspects to bridge the gap between the laboratory and the real application. In particular, all aspects for the setting up of a metal hydride compressor, i.e. selection and characterization of selected metal hydrides, sizing of the plant components, design and the tests aimed to optimize the working performances are presented and deeply discussed, including energy consumption and efficiency necessary to build up a commercial system. The compressor employs two commercial alloys, i.e. a $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Ce}_{0.1}\text{Ni}_5$ from Labtech in the first stage and the Hydralloy-C5 from GfE in the second one. Working between room temperature for absorption and $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for desorption, the hydrogen produced by the electrolyser at 28 bar is compressed up to 250 bar, resulting in a compression ratio of about 9. The metal hydride compressor has a final power consumption of 614 W, of which 85 W are linked to the hydrogen sorption reactions, while other contributions come from the pumps involved in the plant and the dissipations. The compressor presents an isentropic efficiency of about 11% for less than 1 kg of powder in each stage and an average H_2 flowrate of 104 NL/min is observed. The performances of the plant were optimized and maintained for a working time of about 245 h.

Output and results:

- In depth analysis of solid-state reactivity of amino borane through its incorporation into polymer elevate porosity and functionalization.
- In this semester, the compression on site of green hydrogen using metal hydrides was investigated

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

No equipment

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

For the next report:

we will discuss the regeneration procedure regarding the multilayer composites and we will evaluate other waste derived catalyst for hydrogen evolution through water amino borane hydrolysis;

we will discuss the advancement in this specific topic targeting a full modulable reactivity in solid state of chemical hydrogen carriers.

1.2.3 Research Module 3

Research Module n. 3:	Start month: M1	End month: M36					
Title: Hydrogen distribution and transport							
Location in Mezzogiorno: N							
RM Leader	POLITO						
Partners involved	Envipark						
Type of action:	<i>Industrial Research</i>						

Effort in person/months:	POLITO:1,0 1	Envipark:1,3 5					
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Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):

The task aims to develop methods and procedures to design and validate infrastructures for hydrogen distribution and transport

Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):

Task 3.1 Techno-economic analysis and system optimization for renewable infrastructure deployment (POLITO DENERG)

The development of a hydrogen distribution infrastructure with hydrogen generation from RES requires identifying the optimal size and operating strategies of the hydrogen generation and distribution plants to minimize the hydrogen production and distribution cost. The aim of this task is to provide a general methodology for the optimal design of hybrid renewable energy systems for green hydrogen production.

Objective

The general layout of the proposed optimization framework is displayed in Figure 3.1, where the main input and output data are reported. Input parameters to the model include: the technical specifications of the components (efficiency curves, modulation ranges, etc.), time-dependent profiles of hydrogen demand and meteorological data (ambient temperature, solar irradiance, wind velocity), economic data (investment, operation, maintenance and replacement costs, fuel price, discount rate) and constraints (reliability of the energy system, CO₂ emissions, periodicity in the storage levels).

Figure 3.1. Optimization framework developed in this work to carry out the design of the RES-based hydrogen generation system.

The main outputs of the optimization problem are as follows: the sizes of all the system components, the system behavior (power distribution among the components, renewable energy usage and hydrogen coverage over the selected time horizon), economic indicators (levelized cost of hydrogen, net present cost), technical indicators (the lifetime of components, etc.) and environmental indicators (the amount of CO₂ that has been released during the operation). It should be noted that variability in RES production and load requires that the various components continuously adapt their operating point to reliably cover the hydrogen demand and store the surplus renewable energy. Thus, performance curves and modulation ranges have been implemented in the optimal design methodology to simulate the part-load behavior of the devices.

Optimal design methodology

Figure 3.2 reports the various steps that are involved in the optimal design methodology. Once techno-economic input data have been collected, the modelling of all the system components is carried out. Efficiency curves can be included for all the technologies, starting from datasheets or experimental data. The optimal design is then performed with the aim of minimizing the levelized cost of hydrogen.

Figure 3.2. Optimization framework to optimally design the green hydrogen generation system. Focus on electrolysis modelling method as example of component model.

- **Component modeling**

In the optimization framework, components can be included as constant-efficiency elements in the simplest approach, but a specific efficiency model for each component can be also included if a more refined optimization is required. In the following lines an example of component model is provided for the commercial electrolyzers.

Electrochemical models can be formulated for the electrolyzer (alkaline and PEM) devices to obtain an accurate description of their behaviour, which is typically nonlinear. Experimental polarization curves can be used to calibrate the models and compute the value of the fitted parameters. For example, experimental data from Henao *et al.* [1] and Marocco *et al.* [2] are references that can be considered for the validation of the alkaline electrolyzer, PEM electrolyzer models, respectively. Model calibration is carried out by minimizing the mean squared deviation between experimental and model values of the cell operating voltage. The operating cell voltage is described by the reversible voltage increased by irreversible losses including the activation, ohmic and diffusion contributions:

$$V_{cell} = V_{rev} + V_{act} + V_{ohm} + V_{diff}$$

Where V_{rev} (in V) stands for the reversible thermodynamic potential and V_{act} , V_{ohm} and V_{diff} (in V) represent the activation, ohmic and diffusion overpotentials, respectively. A detailed description of all the overvoltage terms can be found in [3]. Based on the electrochemical models, the efficiency (from cell to system level) of

the electrolyzer can be derived. Main input parameters used to evaluate the performance curve are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Main technical input parameters to evaluate the performance curve of the H₂-based technologies

	ALK EL	PEM EL
Operating temperature	70 °C [4]	60 °C [4]
Operating pressure	30 bar [4]	30 bar [4]
System minimum power (% of rated power)	15% [8]	10% [4]
Max. current density	0.35 A/cm ² [5]	1.8 A/cm ² [9]
Aux. consumption in nominal condition (% of rated power)	10% [10]	10% [7], [10]
Aux. consumption in stand-by (% of aux. nom. consumption)	29% [11]	29% [11]

The operating temperature and pressure were taken from [4]. The maximum achievable current density of the alkaline electrolyzer was set to 0.35 A/cm², in line with Refs. [5], [6]. A maximum current density of 1.8 A/cm² was instead considered for the PEM electrolyzer. This value is between 1.7 A/cm² and 2 A/cm², which are reported by Mayyas *et al.* [7] and Parra *et al.*[5], respectively. In order to move from the cell to the system efficiency curve, it is required to know the power consumption due to auxiliary components. It was assumed auxiliary consumption to vary linearly from stand-by to nominal conditions.

Figure 3.3 reports the cell and system efficiency (LHV basis) of the electrochemical devices as a function of the normalized operating power. Nominal specific energy consumptions that were derived from the model are in line with values reported in the literature. Referring to the alkaline electrolyzer system, the obtained nominal value of 5.26 kWh/Nm³ (i.e., LHV efficiency of 0.56) lies in the range 5.0-5.9 kWh/Nm³ [6]. The specific energy consumption of 5.76 kWh/Nm³ (i.e., LHV efficiency of 0.52) computed for the PEM electrolyzer system is also within the reported range of 5.0-6.5 kWh/Nm³ [6]. The system efficiency curves can be then approximated by means of polynomial fitted curves to be used in the optimal sizing problem.

Figure 3.3. Efficiency of the electrolyzer at the selected operating conditions.

- EMS

The fluctuating behaviour of most RESs (e.g., wind and solar) causes variability in the power production that must be properly addressed. Recurrent changes in the operation of the system components, and in particular of the electrolyzer, should be avoided to limit their performance degradation and preserve their lifetime. A battery bank becomes thus useful as an instantaneous and daily energy buffer, smoothing down the RES high-frequency variability. However, the battery device should be protected from heavy utilization, avoiding excessive charging/discharging in order not to negatively affect its life span. Energy management strategies (EMSs) are therefore necessary to operate the various subsystems effectively and safely, while satisfying the hydrogen demand requirements.

Ruled-based (RB)-type EMSs can be applied. The net power, the battery state-of-charge (SOC) and the level of hydrogen (LOH) are the main key decision factor of the proposed EMS. The considered control strategy integrates batteries, as short-term storage system operating in first instance to absorb/provide electricity when necessary, and hydrogen, as longer-term storage medium to satisfy demand fluctuations. A detailed logical block diagram of ruled-based EMS is reported in [4] for a P2P application. Batteries and the hydrogen equipment are allowed to intervene if the SOC and LOH values lie within their lower and upper boundaries, respectively. The electrolyzer is also forced to operate within their modulation ranges. More specifically, whenever the hydrogen demand is higher than the hydrogen production output from the RES-powered electrolyzer, priority of intervention is given to the battery discharging to provide supplementary power to the electrolyzer and allow to reach the hydrogen demand level. The hydrogen storage is then activated to cover the remaining deficit in order to avoid excessive discharging of the battery, keeping the SOC parameter higher than SOC_{min} . Instead, in case the hydrogen demand is lower than the hydrogen producible by renewable power, the surplus RES energy is first used to charge the battery bank until reaching the maximum SOC, then converted into hydrogen through the electrolyzer to refill the hydrogen storage tank and finally curtailed when the hydrogen storage is full. Therefore, in this EMS, batteries act as shorter-term storage operating first when required (and thus limiting the number of start-ups of the electrolyzer); whereas hydrogen works as longer-term storage medium intervening when the upper and lower operating limits of the battery are reached (so as to limit the degradation, and hence loss of performance, of the battery).

- *System sizing*

The particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm can be considered in the optimal sizing problem. The working principle of the PSO-based design optimization process is summarized in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4. Working principle of the metaheuristic-based design optimization algorithm.

The number of elements of each i -th particle (p_i) is equal to the number of decision variables (n_{var}), i.e., sizes of all the components of the system:

$$p_i = [S_{i,1}, S_{i,2}, \dots, S_{i,n_{var}}]$$

Component sizes to be optimized were also imposed to vary between specific lower and upper bounds:

$$S_{i,j,min} \leq S_{i,j} \leq S_{i,j,max}$$

where $S_{i,j}$ is the size of the j -th component referred to the i -th particle. $S_{i,j,min}$ was set to 0 for all the variables. During the PSO main loop, the velocities and positions of the particles were iteratively changed until reaching one of the following stopping criteria:

- Reaching a maximum number of iterations equal to It_{MAX} ;
- No changes in 30 iterations for the global best position (relative change less than 10^{-6}).

It_{MAX} is the maximum number of iterations, which should be chosen high enough so as not to be reached. A value of 100 can be considered for the size of population (i.e., number of particles in the swarm). The weighting coefficients of the personal best and global best positions can be set to 2, as also suggested in the literature [12]-[14]. As displayed in Figure 3.4, an inner layer was implemented in the PSO algorithm to deal with the system operation and subsequent evaluation of the objective function, i.e., the levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH). The inner layer structure is shown in Figure 3.5. Based on the input meteorological and load data, it is first performed hour by hour the energy simulation of the system over a specific time horizon (a reference year) by means of pre-defined ruled-based control strategies. An economic analysis is subsequently carried out with the aim of evaluating the levelized cost of hydrogen, which has to be minimized by the optimization problem. The cost of hydrogen can be finally penalized to discourage and discard the solutions where some specific constraints are not satisfied.

Figure 3.5. Schematic of the inner layer dealing with the system operation and LCOH evaluation.

- **Objective function**

The LCOH is computed according to the following relationship:

$$LCOE = \frac{C_{NPC,tot}}{\sum_{j=1}^n \frac{H_j}{(1+d)^j}}$$

where $C_{NPC,tot}$ (in €) is the total net present cost, H_j (in MWh or kg) is the hydrogen supplied by the system during the j -th year, n is the lifetime of the project and d is the real discount rate. The total net present cost is given by the sum of the present value of all the costs incurred by the system (capital, OM and replacement contributions) minus the present value of all the revenues (i.e., salvage contributions) over the lifetime of the project:

$$C_{NPC,tot} = C_{inv,tot} + C_{NPC,OM,tot} + C_{NPC,rep,tot} - C_{NPC,sal,tot}$$

The various terms that are included in the above NPC formula (in €) are the investment, operation and maintenance (OM), replacement and salvage costs.

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wind-FC system for remote area in Egypt,” *Renew. Energy*, vol. 95, pp. 367–380, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2016.04.030.

Task 3.2 Test procedures/protocols for leak tests on an innovative heat exchanger for HRS application (ENVIPARK).

The activities are designed to accompany the development of innovative heat exchangers and continued on the basis of the evidence gathered during the first project period. Test protocols were defined to verify the leakage of the exchangers using helium as the test gas under the defined pressure conditions. A test infrastructure was designed and set up and the first equipment validation campaigns were conducted.

Task 3.3 Hydrogen distribution via natural gas transport and distribution net (POLITO DISAT)

The distribution of gases through commercial pipelines often leads to mixtures that require separation, notably the separation of hydrogen from methane. Membranes have presented themselves as a forward-looking solution in this domain. These semi-permeable barriers operate using mechanisms like solution/diffusion and molecular sieving to achieve efficient separation. The choice of a particular membrane hinges on its physical and chemical attributes tailored to separate specific gas duos. The efficacy of these membranes primarily depends on two key parameters: permeability, which denotes the rate of compound transition through the membrane, and selectivity, which signifies the propensity of the membrane to favor one gas over another.

Although polymer-based membranes play a significant role in this field, they often grapple with a balance between permeability and selectivity. This is where Mixed Matrix Membranes (MMMs) come into play.

MMMs ingeniously integrate inorganic constituents into a polymeric framework. This amalgamation aims to combine the easy processing of polymers with the superior gas separation qualities inherent to inorganic materials. The goal is to efficiently separate hydrogen from methane post-distribution, optimizing energy and cost-effectiveness. However, challenges such as scalability for commercial production and cost concerns remain. Still, MMMs hold immense promise for revolutionizing post-distribution gas separation processes.

In recent months, a comprehensive study was undertaken on synthesizing and employing PIM with high specific gas separation attributes. The steps and methodologies are detailed below: PIM-1 Synthesis: PIM-1, a prominent material, was synthesized using Tetramethyl-1,1-spirobiindane and Tetrafluoroterephthalonitrile as primary reactants. The reaction was executed in a meticulously controlled, deoxygenated setting and persisted for a duration of 72 hours. Upon completion of this phase, the resultant substance was subjected to purification processes. The end product was a distinct yellow powder. cPIM-1 Synthesis: An evolution of the PIM-1, termed cPIM-1, was derived by initiating a hydrolysis reaction on PIM-1. The purpose of this reaction was to convert the existing nitrile group into a carboxylic group. Post-reaction, the product underwent procedures like washing, neutralization, and subsequent drying. Mesoporous Carbons Synthesis: Another critical component in our research was the mesoporous carbons. These were extracted from readily available commercial chitosan. The preparation technique involved microwave-assisted pyrolysis, which was executed under a protective nitrogen atmosphere. cPIM-1 based Membrane Preparation: For the membrane formation, cPIM-1 was initially dissolved in judiciously chosen solvents. The solvent casting technique was then employed to fabricate the membranes. In order to ascertain optimal conditions for the formation of these membranes, various supports such as glass petri dishes, nylon, and PTFE were experimented with. cPIM-1 and Carbons Composite Membrane: Building on the previously determined best practices for membrane formation, cPIM-1 was amalgamated with the synthesized carbons to prepare a composite membrane. The methodology incorporated solubilizing both cPIM-1 and the carbons in specific solvents. This mixture was then cast and subjected to drying to finalize the membrane creation. In conclusion, the prepared samples resulting from these methodologies are currently under rigorous examination. The aim is to ascertain their viability and efficiency in gas separation, thereby potentially heralding a new era in gas separation technologies.

Output and results:

Optimization models have been applied to the design of hybrid renewable energy systems for green hydrogen production.

development of innovative heat exchangers.

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

No equipment

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

Activities will follow with the consolidation of test protocols and infrastructure and their application on prototype heat exchangers.

1.2.4 Research Module 4

Research Module n. 4:	Start month: M1	End month: M36
Title: E-fuels: CO2 recovery and conversion		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	POLITO	
Partners involved	UNITO	
Type of action:	<i>Industrial Research</i>	
Effort in person/months:	POLITO:0,22	UNITO:0,30

Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):

Research work has been focused on the development of catalysts for hydrogenating CO₂ to methanol.

Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):

Task 4.1

(POLITO DISAT)

In the second semester, the study focuses on comparing two different methodologies for preparing Na-promoted Fe₃O₄-based catalysts for the hydrogenation of CO₂ into hydrocarbon mixtures. Three catalysts were synthesized and tested: two samples were impregnated with a different amount of Na (1 wt% and 5 wt%), while a third one was obtained via coprecipitation with NaOH. As the latter catalyst exhibited the best performance, it was combined with zeolites in two ways: physical mixtures and core-shell structures. MFI-type zeolites were used in both configurations and a conventional structure was compared to a hierarchical one.

The basic general result was that mesopores increased successfully both the conversion of CO₂ from 37% to 40% and the liquid hydrocarbon (C₆+) selectivity from 29% to 57%, doubling the C yield. On the other hand, NH₃-TPD and XPS measurements demonstrated that the intimate contact between the two materials in the core-shell structures led to the migration of Na from the oxide to the zeolite reducing the concentration of strong acid sites and, consequently, the liquid hydrocarbon yield.

(UNITO)

Research in the UNITO team has been focused on combining previous results on CO₂ capture materials, with novel reduction functionality leading to synthetic fuels. In particular, two different capture platforms were considered as candidates to host reductive functionalization: Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) and MgO loaded zeolites. In MOFs, active hydrogenation active centers may be introduced either as structural metal coordination complexes or as additional extra-framework sites coordinated to modified linkers. Synthetic strategies for both approaches are currently under development and a first generation of adsorbers/catalysts based on the UiO-67 MOF framework has been synthesized, whose characterization is ongoing. The first characterization results are expected to appear in the next Periodic Report. Concerning MgO/Y zeolites, the activity is less advanced. The guiding principle is the synthesis of highly uncoordinated MgO clusters, which

have been demonstrated to provide reversible carbonate formation, and to decorate these clusters with redox-active metal sites, active in the hydrogenation of the carbonates.

Output and results:

The expected results can be summarized into the production of a synergic structure between the sodium promoted iron oxides and a mesoporous zeolite to significantly improve the yield of the hydrogenation of carbon dioxide.

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

No equipment

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

Suitable synthesis routes have been envisaged and the materials have been procured, with the synthesis planned for the next reporting period.

1.2.5 Research Module

Explain the work carried out in RM5 during the reporting period by providing details of the activities carried out by each beneficiary/affiliated entity involved.

Research Module n. 5:	Start month: M1	End month: M36
Title: E-fuels: Technologies, components and applications for FC mobility		
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y		
RM Leader	POLITO	
Partners involved	CNR-ITM	ENVIPARK
Type of action:	Industrial Research	
Effort in person/months:	POLITO:8,07	CNR-ITM: 7,91
		Envipark:2,81

Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):

Development of new ionic conductive membranes, analysis of innovative technologies for FC manufacturing, design of high efficiency and low incumbrance and mass air compressors for air supply, design of application of FC to road and water mobility, design of novel mechanical bearings for high speed rotors to avoid air compressors in FC-based mobile applications.

Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):

Summary of the activities envisaged

Task 5.1 New strategies for ionic conductive membranes

(CNR-ITM)

Summary

Membrane based electrochemical processes for energy conversion like polymer electrolyte fuel cells (PEMFC) can contribute fulfilling the increasing world's energy demand without emitting greenhouse gases. However, these technologies are still limited not only by economic and technical barriers related to membrane cost and performance, but

also by environmental issues related to membrane fabrication. The main objective of this task is the development of a sustainable protocol for the production of high performing membranes using non-toxic solvents to replace substances of very high concern (SVHC) traditionally used in the state-of-the-art preparation protocols of polymer electrolyte membranes (PEM). Perfluorosulfonic acid (PFSA) polymers were selected as membrane material because they are still most performing and characterized by higher durability in comparison to non-fluorinated membranes. However, our approach can be extended also to non-fluorinated materials used for the preparation of PEMs by solution casting techniques. Several non-toxic and green solvents were evaluated using the Hansen Solubility Parameters (HSP) to predict their affinity toward the Nafion (a PFSA membrane widely used in PEMFC). Based on the results, four biobased solvents were selected as green solvents for Nafion membranes preparation, and in general for the substitution of toxic polar aprotic solvents such as, 1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP), dimethylacetamide (DMA) and dimethylformamide (DMF), frequently used in PEM preparation.

Output and results

Membrane-based operations are generally considered by themselves green and sustainable; however, it is frequently overlooked that the membrane fabrication itself is quite far to be green. Most of the solvents used in industrially relevant membranes productions are hazardous to human health and to the environment and are also currently mentioned as substances of very high concern (SVHC) in different lists guides, such as REACH and EPA¹. It's worth to note that the three more frequently used solvents for polymeric membrane preparation (i.e. NMP, DMA and DMF)² are classified as SVHC, because of their serious health hazards (Table 1).

Table 1. Classification of solvents frequently used in membrane preparation as substances of very high concern (SVHC) according to Article 59(10) of the REACH Regulation (<https://echa.europa.eu/it/candidate-list-table>)

Substance name	N. CE	N. CAS	Date of inclusion	Reason for inclusion	Decision	Pictograms
1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP)	212-828-1	872-50-4	20-giu-2011	Toxic for reproduction (Article 57c)	ED/31/2011	
N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMA)	204-826-4	127-19-5	19-dic-2011	Toxic for reproduction (Article 57c)	ED/77/2011	
N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF)	200-679-5	68-12-2	19-dic-2012	Toxic for reproduction (Article 57c)	ED/169/2012	

Serious health hazard

Health Hazard

Flammable

Corrosive

Therefore, there is great attention today to develop innovative production protocols where harmful solvents are replaced by not toxic substances, to make industrial membrane production more environmentally friendly.³ Our approach in this project is a combined theoretical and experimental evaluation of green alternative solvents compliant with REACH and EPA regulations for the development of efficient green protocols for next generation polymer electrolyte membranes for fuel cells.

Thirteen different non-toxic solvents were selected as possible alternative to SVHC (#1-3; DMA, DMF and NMP, respectively): six with petrochemical origin (#4-10); two biosolvents (#11-12) and four blends of chemicals with high content of biosourced raw materials (#13-16).

The affinity for Nafion was estimated using Hansen solubility parameters.⁴ Solvents and polymers can be characterised by three parameters: δ_d for dispersion, δ_p for polar and δ_h for hydrogen bonding. The Nafion and the selected solvents were represented as points in a three-dimensional space called HSP space (Figure 5.1a). Substance with high affinity have similar HSP (or “like dissolves like”). Quantitative evaluation of the solubility of a polymer in a solvent can be represented by the value of R_a [(MPa)^{1/2}], which reflects the distance between the HSPs of both substances:

¹ Green Chem. 2016, 18, 288-296

² Journal of Membrane Science 2021, 622, 1189872

³ Green Chem., 2014, 16, 4034-4059

⁴ J. Chem. Inf. Model. 2019, 59, 10, 4188-4194

$$R_a = [4(\delta_{dp}-\delta_{ds})^2 + (\delta_{pp}-\delta_{ps})^2 + (\delta_{hp}-\delta_{hs})^2]^{1/2}$$

where the second subscript refer to polymer (p) or solvent (s)

On the basis of empirical considerations, solvents within $R_a \leq 5 \text{ MPa}^{1/2}$ are usually good solvents for a given polymer, and those with $R_a > 5 \text{ MPa}^{1/2}$ are supposed to be non-solvents⁵. Our calculations indicated a good compatibility of the Nafion with the green solvents #4-6; #11, #13-16 (Figure 1b).

Figure 5.1. (a) Distribution and (b) calculated distance polymer/solvent (R_a) in HSPs space. Codes used: #1-3: DMA, DMF and NMP, respectively; #4-10: non-toxic solvents with petrochemical origin; #11-12: biosolvents; #13-16: blends of chemicals with high content of biosourced raw materials

The solvency power was experimentally investigated dispersing Nafion at various concentration in the 16 solvents. The experimental results were in good agreement with theoretical calculations, except for solvent #10 and #11. Considering that biobased solvents have a lower carbon footprint with respect to petrochemicals-based solvents⁶, the solvents #13-16 were used to produce Nafion membranes by solution casting technique (Figure 5.2)

Figure 5.2. Image of Nafion membranes samples produced using bio-based solvents #13-16

Preliminary results indicate an higher stability of the membranes prepared using the solvents #13 and #14, but further studies are in progress.

⁵ D. W. Van Krevelen, Properties of Polymers, Their correlation with chemical structure, Their numerical estimation and prediction from additive group contributions, Elsevier Amsterdam, 1990

⁶ Kim, D., & Nunes, S. P. (2020). Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry, 100427.

5.1.1 Synthesis of microporous polymer based on benzimidazole groups fluorine-free for proton exchange membrane fuel cells (POLITO DISAT)

In the realm of proton exchange membranes, Nafion has emerged as a predominant choice owing to its exceptional proton conductivity coupled with impressive flexibility. Yet, an intrinsic limitation characterizing Nafion is its reliance on water, thereby confining its operational temperature to a ceiling of 90 degrees Celsius.

This research year was dedicated to probing alternative materials, with an emphasis on the intrinsically microporous polymer (PIM). The *raison d'être* for this shift was to harness the potential of PIM by substituting its inherent -CN group with a benzimidazole group. This adaptation was premised on the well-documented stability properties exhibited by polybenzimidazole.

As part of our methodological approach, the initial phase entailed the synthesis of PIM1. Progressing further, a derivative known as cPIM-1 was synthesized.

Figure 5.3: cPIM production starting from PIM-1

This variant is distinctive, with its -CN group being substituted by a more functional -COOH group. One of the more intricate aspects of this research was the synthesis of Benzimidazole-PIM. This process presented a series of complexities, most notably those related to solubility parameters and the fine-tuning of operational conditions. However, driven by methodical experimentation and iterative testing regimes, we succeeded in establishing an optimized synthesis protocol for Benzimidazole-PIM.

Figure 5.4: bPIM production starting from cPIM

Figure 5.5: a) bPIM production b) Chemical characterization

Post-synthesis, our focus shifted to empirical evaluations. A comprehensive series of solvent compatibility tests were instituted to ascertain the membrane's adaptability. Concurrently, efforts were channeled towards membrane production. It's noteworthy to mention that this phase was not devoid of challenges. The intricacies of the membrane-laying process demanded rigorous attention to detail. Yet, the culmination of these efforts bore fruit, as the empirical results underscored the effectiveness of our novel synthesis procedure.

Figure 5.6: bPIM filmed on a petri dish

In summation, the endeavors of this research year have illuminated a potential pathway to redefining standards in proton exchange membrane technology, promising enhanced operational temperatures and efficiency.

5.1.2 MEA fabrication and electrochemical characterization for fuel cells application (POLITO DISAT)

Since the optimization of the nanostructure of cathode catalyst layer (CL) plays a pivotal role to reduce the oxygen transport resistance at the cathode of polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells (PEMFC), the main objective of research activities, at this stage of the project, was to optimize the initial ink, based on Pt/C. To this purpose the composition of initial ink, with a main focus onto the solvent composition catalyst ink, represents the decisive factor for the wetting behavior of the ink solution on the GDL and is the key to optimize the 3-phase-boundary. Among all possible techniques, involved to distribute and create a proper catalyst layer, we selected ultrasonic spray coating process (USC) to ensure continuous and uniform deposition of the catalytic layer. One of the great advantages of USC process is its ability to

deposit CLs directly onto carbon paper, properly modified with a microporous layer (MPL-CP). We started with the following ink composed of catalyst powders (10wt% of Pt onto carbon, purchased from Sigma Aldrich), ionomer solution (5wt% of Nafion in water) and solvents isopropanol and deionized water (IPA: DI) with a volume ratio of 3:4.

We investigated and compared two different amounts of Pt/C, respectively equal to 0.5 mg cm^{-2} and 0.125 mg cm^{-2} . The size of ink droplets landing on the polymer electrolyte membrane was controlled using ultrasonic nozzles at the frequencies of 90 kHz, while, on the contrary, a substrate temperature of 80°C was imposed. This temperature affected the solvent evaporation, that consequently influences the pores distribution. The larger are the pores, the lower is cathode-flooding, leading thus to enhance mass transport of oxygen. This research activity has resulted in/led to design a gas diffusion electrode (GDE) composed by carbon paper with a microporous layer, on which catalyst layer, based on 0.5 mg cm^{-2} Pt/C was deposited by implementing USC. This GDE was subsequently tested in a gas diffusion setup testing, which allows characterization of realistic fuel cell catalyst layers at application relevant current densities and potentials. In GED setup, moreover, this designed carbon-based electrode was directly interface with the commercial Nafion® NR-211 membrane to mimic the configuration closest to that of the MEA. **Figure 5.7** reports the first obtained results confirmed the good electro-catalytic activity of GDE exposing ultrasonic-spray coating Pt/C onto carbon paper. Indeed, polarization curves, determining the ORR performance of developed GDE, allowed highlighting a negative current at low overpotential values.

Figure 5.7 Cyclic voltammetry curves to estimate the electrochemical active surface area, conducted under N₂- atmosphere and polarization curves that have a key role in determining the ORR performance of analyzed GDEs.

Task 5.2 Innovative technologies for FC manufacturing and analysis of automation processes in stack packaging and production (ENVIPARK; POLITO DISAT)

5.2.1 Analysis of innovative plasma-based technologies for FC manufacturing (ENVIPARK)

The semester's activities have been focused on the initiation of the state-of-the-art analysis related to the use of plasma technologies in the manufacturing of electrochemical conversion devices employing hydrogen (fuel

cell and electrolysers). The activity saw interaction with some international technology providers to gain information on the latest developments in terms of processes and enabling technologies.

In particular, the processes examined mainly involved treatments designed to improve the adhesion of components of different materials (surface cleaning, activation and deposition); in addition, there has been a rise in sealing treatments intended for anti-corrosion coating. These preliminary tasks have therefore been laid for the next activities which will also have an experimental dimension geared toward testing new deposition technologies with the aim of eliminating solvent-based primers and adhesives from processes.

Following the initial phase of exploring the possible solutions in terms of creating coatings with dual adhesive and anti-corrosion functionality, deposition tests were carried out using various industrially sustainable solutions. For this purpose, preliminary steel samples are being produced which will be subjected to tests and characterizations. The technology used is Plasmatrete deposition technology (Plasma Plus), a solution that allows integration into various types of movement systems. A program of in-depth workshops lasting a working week has been defined which aims to exchange experiences and skills on the topics covered by the study with the participation of technology providers.

5.2.2 Laser-based processing of nanostructured carbon electrodes for FC (POLITO DISAT)

As anticipated in the first progress report completed in May 2023, the preparation of graphene foams via laser treatment of polymers as polyimides has gained success since it combines simplicity to high speed. The resulting material is usually referred to as laser-induced graphene (LIG). To the best of our knowledge applications of LIG in proton-exchange membrane fuel cells (PEM-FCs) is still unexplored.

In this second progress review we report the results we obtained up to now investigating LIG obtained from sulfonated polyether ether ketone (SPEEK) films (LIG-S).

The photothermal process initiated by the laser scribe on SPEEK allowed the nearly complete conversion of thin SPEEK films into LIG-S. The picture of fabricated sample is shown in **Figure 5.8a**), and the detail of the carbonized surface is proposed in **Figure 5.8b**). LIG-S sample is mostly composed of carbon, as confirmed by the Raman spectrum proposed in **Figure 5.8c**). The Raman spectrum displayed the three typical peaks of graphitic carbon. The D peak at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is activated by single-phonon intervalley scattering mediated by defective sites in the graphitic lattice. The G peak at 1580 cm^{-1} is the fingerprint of sp^2 carbon lattices. Finally, the second-order 2D peak at $\sim 2700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is extremely sensitive to the stacking order of graphitic layers and is originated by scattering events involving two zone-boundary phonons. The ratio between the integrated intensities of the D and G peaks is an indicator of the crystallinity of the sample. In this case, $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}} \approx 0.7$ signals highly crystallized material, with a crystallite size about 24 nm. The final LIG-S results to be a few-layer graphene with randomly stacked layers, a structure also known as turbostratic.

Figure 5.8. (a) LIG-S onto CP at the end of the laser scribing process; (b) Low magnification FESEM of the LIG-S surface; (c) Raman spectrum of LIG-S: D peak $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$, G peak $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and 2D peak $\sim 2700\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Moreover, electrochemical tests in rotating disk and half-cell setups highlight the intrinsic catalytic activity of LIG towards the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) occurring at the cathode electrode. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) were performed with an inert nitrogen gas in both the RRDE and GDE experiments (see Task 5.3.2 for more info).

Results for RRDE are shown in **Figure 5.9**, while **Figure 5.10** refers to the GDE experiments.

Figure 5.9. (a) CV at a 10 mV/s scan rate in nitrogen and oxygen shows ORR activity. Both RRDE and GDE setups returned a curve with identical features. Here, only the GDE one is reported; (b) RRDE disk and ring current comparison; (c) average detected number of electrons involved in the ORR (left axis) and percentage of reduced HO_2^- (right axis); (d) RRDE Nyquist plot showing an evident charge transfer.

An intrinsic ORR activity of the LIG-S sample emerged from both CV and LSV in both setups, as significantly higher negative (cathodic) currents were detected with oxygen gas than with nitrogen gas, as displayed in **Figure 5.9a)** and **Figure 5.10a)**.

Figure 10. (a) LSV at 5 mV/s scan rate in nitrogen, oxygen, and net current in the GDE setup; (b) GDE Nyquist plot showing a more sluggish charge transfer than in the RRDE setup.

Analyzing the RRDE data of **Figure 5.8b)** it is possible to appreciate high disk currents and low ring currents across the range of relevant operating voltages. This result indicates that the preferred reaction site was at the LIG-S surface. An impressive stability was observed in the average number of electrons involved in the ORR, as represented in **Figure 5.8c)**. The number of electrons peaked at 3.75 and never decreased below 3.5. These values are remarkably close to the ideal four-electron number obtained with platinum catalysts. Further confirmation came from the amount of oxygen undergoing two consecutive two-electron reactions, which is quantified by the amount of HO_2^- further reduced to water by the platinum ring. As represented in **Figure 5.8c)**, the amount of hydrogen peroxide always remained below 10% across the entire voltage range, solidifying the previous findings.

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) was performed in both RRDE and GDE setups at -0.2 V, corresponding to the ORR current peak of LIG-S. In both cases, the frequency spanned the 1 Hz to 100 kHz range, and the superimposed signal had an amplitude of 10 mV. The Nyquist plot derived in the RRDE experiment, which is displayed in **Figure 5.8d)**, depicted a clear charge transfer with a characteristic time constant equal to 0.4 ms. The impedance semicircle was diffusion-limited only towards the lower end of the frequency range. Instead, the Nyquist plot derived in the GDE experiment highlighted a more sluggish charge transfer across the entire voltage range, in which the diffusion-limited portion took over at higher frequencies than in the RRDE setup. As a result, the charge transfer semicircle was overall less defined, as it is possible to see in **Figure 5.10b)**. A high-frequency inductive component appeared only in the GDE Nyquist plot and was attributed to the electrical wiring connecting the GDE setup to the electrochemical workstation. In GDE setup oxygen reaches the reaction sites by diffusion through the porous electrode, and a true three-phase boundary is formed at the GDE–electrolyte interface. This process can explain the slightly sluggish charge transfer observed in the GDE tests. Nonetheless, the ORR activity observed in the RRDE setup translated relatively well into the GDE half-cell setup, proving that the LIG-S can function as a PEM-FC gas diffusion electrode.

This catalytic activity observed for the LIG-S nanomaterial is attributed to structural defects in the LIG lattice and sulfur doping incorporated from the SPEEK precursor. and it may lower the catalyst loading required to reach competitive cell performance.

5.2.3 Electrohydrodynamic methods for catalysts deposition (POLITO DISAT)

In the previous progress report, we described the first experiments we performed, investigating the use of the electrospray process to be used for catalyst deposition. During this semester we continued the analysis of this electrohydrodynamic process to deposit Pt-based inks but the problems discussed in the first report have not yet been solved. As already discussed, we are tried to optimize the composition of the initial solution in order to achieve a uniform distribution of nanodrops on the substrate surface. As proposed in May 2023, we tried to reduce the amount of the polymer (i.e. Nafion) to promote nanodrops formation, but our trials failed. Unfortunately, up to now non-uniformity and incomplete solvent removal still characterize the result.

In the next period we will explore the use of polymers alternatives to Nafion for the electrohydrodynamic deposition.

5.2.4 Microwave Synthesis of Pt-free catalysts for PEMFCs (POLITO DISAT)

During the previous reporting period the catalytic behavior of LIG-nanostructured electrodes (i.e., nanostructured laser induced graphene (LIG) electrode based on nanofibers (NFs) made of Polyacrylonitrile – PAN) have been characterized by RRDE. During this reporting period, in Task 5.2.2, the full electrochemical characterization of LIG-S electrodes has been reported. The aim in the following reporting period is to test both those nanostructured, carbon-based electrodes for the processing by microwave reactor to improve their catalytic behavior by activating a co-doping process.

Task 5.3 Test procedures/protocols for FC and components (ENVIPARK; POLITO-DISAT)

5.3.1 (ENVIPARK)

The activities included the definition of testing protocols related to bipolar plates for PEM fuel cells. In this period preliminary activities have been carried out to set the framework conditions to define the experimental needs.

5.3.2 (POLITO-DISAT)

In this project we want to contribute to the development of protocols useful to test FC components. To this purpose We already introduced in the previous progress report our interest to optimize the test of the catalysts for the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) occurring at the cathode of PEM-FCs. To reach this goal different electrochemical setups can be used. Among these, the rotating ring disk electrode (RRDE) setup is generally the most commonly uses, as it allows fast determination of the intrinsic ORR activity of a catalyst. The four-electrode RRDE setup can quantify the amount of oxygen that is reduced to water via the direct four-electron reaction, which is the faster and preferred path, as well as the amount of oxygen that undergoes two successive two-electron reactions. More recently, gas diffusion electrode (GDE) setups have been established as an intermediate step between RRDE and full cell setups. They have also been defined as half-cell setups, in which the electrolyte is still liquid but the full GDE is being tested. The oxygen gas reaches the reaction sites by diffusion through the porous electrode, and a true three-phase boundary is formed at the GDE–electrolyte interface (H^+ ions in the liquid electrolyte, gaseous oxygen fuel, and solid-state catalyst). During the timeframe of the project our interest is to optimize the measurement protocol for testing with the GDE setup, and then extending the optimization to single chamber measurements.

During this semester the GDE method has been used to test LIG-S electrodes as described in Task 5.2.2.

Task 5.4 Fuel cells stack modeling and BoP design (POLITO-DENERG; ENVIPARK)

The activity performed is the development of a dynamic model at system level of a small-size PEMFC stack for the design of control strategies to be implemented at vehicle level. The model has been developed in Simulink (Simscape), which is Simscape well-suited for dynamic simulation of complex systems with multiple domains connected, such as thermal, liquid, and electrical domains. The model schematic is shown in Figure 5.11.

Figure 5.11. Model of PEMFC (Simulink) including MEA, cooling system, anode and cathode channels

The input for the model is the electrical load that the PEMFC stack has to cover in terms of power. The Membrane Electrode Assembly (MEA) model simulates the relation between voltage and current in the stack. In the MEA model, the voltage cell is equivalent to the Open Voltage Circuit (OCV) – modeled using Nernst's equation – minus the activation, ohmic and diffusion overpotentials. The relation between cell current and gases (hydrogen and oxygen) consumption and water production is implemented as Faraday's Law. The heat produced in the stack is calculated as contribution of reaction heat and cell heating due to irreversibilities. The MEA model includes also the water balance within the membrane. The anode and cathode channels, both inside the stack and outside at the source/exhaust pipes are included as separate (i.e. from the MEA) models that simulate the dynamic flow of the fluids taking into account the viscous losses that generates pressure drops and the convective heat transfer with the walls. Mass, momentum and energy conservation equations are implemented in the two models. As the fuel cell over-heating has to be avoided, a cooling system strategy, control and model is necessary. The heat produced by the stack is evaluated in the MEA model and the increasing temperature stack's mass is modelled as a lumped thermal mass component. The heat exchanged by the stack to the coolant water is modelled as a pipe component in the thermal liquid domain. The hydrogen source model can simulate either a hydrogen tank or a metal hydride tank. The simulation results for the dynamic response a 300 W PEMFC stack (with metal hydride storage) is shown in Figure 5.12.

Figure 5.12. Simulation results for a 300 W PEMFC stack.

The model is able to reproduce the experimental behavior of the PEMFC stack, both from the electrical and thermal point of view as shown in Figure 5.13.

Figure 5.13. Simulation vs. Experimental results of PEMFC model.

Task 5.5 FC powered small hydrogen electric propelled boat (POLITO-DIMEAS)

It was considered appropriate to undertake a study and modeling phase to find the tools for the design. In particular, the work has focused on:

- Study of a possible architecture of the hydrogen driveline
- Fuel-cell modelling in Simulink

Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) Fuel Cells (FC) have been considered, as they are low-operating-temperature fuel cells intended for use in mass production vehicles that are currently under development.

Study of the architecture of the fuel cell power system

From the system design point of view, the fuel cell can be seen as a battery, as it converts chemical energy from reactants into electricity. However, there are two aspects that must be considered for applying fuel cell to electric vehicles for maritime transports. The first one is the fuel cell slow transient response to load changes. The second one involves design and control of the Balance of Plant (BOP), i.e. of the additional component that are needed to properly operate the fuel cell [1].

To address the slow dynamic response, it should be considered to couple the fuel cell with some form of energy storage with a quick charge/discharge capability. This can be realized with a hybrid fuel cell-battery configuration. A possible schematic of the system architecture for the electric boat is shown in Figure 5.144.

Figure 5.14. FC powered boat system architecture. Single solid lines refer to FC circuits. Paired solid lines indicate power signals. Dashed lines represent control signals.

The main components are:

- *Hydrogen tank*: The tank pressure is assumed to be 350 bar in order to store a significant amount of hydrogen in a relatively compact space. A *pressure regulator* between tank and FC is required to regulate H₂ flow rate through the anode inlet. Higher pressure tanks, up to 700 bar, could be considered in the future.
- *PEM FC*: it will be responsible for generating electrical power with a desired net output power. In order for the FC to function properly and efficiently, auxiliary components must be considered:
 - *Hydrogen circulating system*: it is needed to improve the utilization of hydrogen. To avoid gas accumulation of inserts and impurities, purging the circulating system may also be required.

- *Humidifier*: humidifiers are essential to ensure the overall performance and reliability of the system. Without humidification, the fuel cell membrane becomes too dry and reduces the proton transport in the HFC, decreasing the oxygen reduction reaction at the cathode resulting in HFC malfunction.
- *Cooling system*: it takes care of dissipating the heat produced, thus maintaining the ideal temperature for the correct functioning of the fuel cell. Active air cooling can be achieved through the use of ventilation fans or water pumps.
- *Sensors*: sensors to monitor pressures, air and hydrogen flows, temperature, voltages, currents and power output from the system.
- *Air Compressor*: A compressor will be needed for the air circuit in order to guarantee the flow required by the cell.
- *Exhaust circuit*: there will be an exhaust circuit to manage the by-products and effluents generated during the operation of the FC.
- *Battery and Battery charge/discharge unit*: the battery pack acts as an energy support when the power required by the electric motor differs from the nominal power supplied by the HFC. In addition, the battery pack plays an important role in managing transients that may occur due to sudden load variations.
- *DC/DC Converter*: To ensure proper integration between FC, battery pack, motor and auxiliary, more than one DC/DC may be needed. For example, one DC/DC converter to regulate voltage for auxiliary loads of the FC, and one to supply a different voltage level to batteries and motor.
- *Electric motor*: The electric motor, either DC or AC (in this case a DC/AC inverter is required), will absorb requested power mainly from the FC. During transients, peaks will be supported by the battery pack.
- *Boat controller*: A control unit will be responsible for the overall management of the system, including monitoring of components, power control, interface management between different components and general system safety.
- *BOP controller*: it will respond to the Boat controller, and is in charge of controlling auxiliary components of the FC.

The scheme described shows how the proper functioning of a hydrogen propulsion system requires a close integration between the various subsystems. For this, it was considered essential to address a phase of study and modeling of the key element, namely the fuel cell, and of the complete system.

PEM Fuel cell model

Matlab Simulink has been considered for FC modelling. Depending on the fidelity level, different approaches can be used. For instance, Mathworks offers [2]:

- two built-in blocks that can be used in Simscape;
- the possibility to model FC through statistical model in Matlab;
- an example of a more precise modelling in Simulink.

The difference between these models is also explained in a dedicated webinar [3]. A graphical classification is reported in Figure 5.155.15. For the best integration of the element shown in Figure 5.144, the Simulink approach has been chosen in this project. In fact, compared to the Simscape blocks, it permits to consider the FC dynamics, which is a key aspect for this study.

The example by Mathworks is a good starting point; however, third-party models can be tricky to handle when the addition of other subsystem is needed, as they usually are built for demonstration or general purposes, that differs from the one shown in figure 5.20. Moreover, by observing the Simulink example, a more detailed modelling of BOP components is desired, as well as the integration of additional subsystems. This would allow for more complete control strategies, that may act at the level of all FC auxiliary and circuits. For instance, observing the scheme in figure 5.20, it is fundamental optimizing the efficiency of the FC and providing the required power to the motor even during transient loads. Thus, control strategies should manage, among others:

- Temperature humidity and gas flow rates of the FC.
- Charging/discharging of the batteries according to the FC and system dynamics.

For this, a custom model has been built. The model is described in the following section.

Figure 5.15. Different approaches for PEM FC modelling within the Matlab environment [3]

Custom FC model

This section describes the model of the PEM Fuel Cell in Simulink. First, the model in question uses the equations that govern the electrochemistry behind the production of electrical energy [1], that involve reagents (hydrogen and oxygen), reaction potential and related losses. Then, in order to obtain a scheme that is able to represent as faithfully as possible the real behavior of a FC, the whole dynamics of the gases entering and leaving the cell and their respective sources are considered. Moreover, all the external components necessary to maximize the efficiency of the cell are modeled. The block diagram of the FC model is shown in Figure 5.16.

Figure 5.16. FC block diagram in Simulink

The central block models the MEA (Membrane Electrode Assembly). Inside MEA block there are the equations that define the cell potential generation, the electric power production, the resulting heat, and the diffusion and utilization of the reactants in the polymer membrane. The electrical component of the cell can be seen as an equivalent circuit where there is an open

circuit potential (see Figure5.17), from which all the losses that result from the operation will be subtracted. Potential losses of the dynamic and static types, are due to activation and concentration resistances (R_d) and ohmic resistances (R_i).

Figure5.17. Equivalent electric circuit of the cell

In particular, the open circuit potential, or Nernst potential, is defined by the equation [4]:

$$E = E_0 + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln\left(\frac{a_{H_2} a_{O_2}^{0.5}}{a_{H_2O}}\right)$$

Where E_0 is the potential under standard conditions, while a_i are the activities of the reactants and products.

Losses must be subtracted from this potential [5]:

- Activation losses (Tafel equation): $V = \frac{RT}{2\alpha F} \ln\left(\frac{i_{cell}}{i_0}\right)$, where i_0 is the exchange current density and α the charge coefficient.
- Concentration losses: $V = \frac{RT}{2F} \ln\left(1 - \frac{i_{cell}}{i_L}\right)$, where i_L is the max current density beyond which the cell is damaged.
- Ohmic losses: $V = \frac{i_{cell}}{\sigma_{membrane}} t_{membrane}$, where $\sigma_{membrane}$ and $t_{membrane}$ are the conductivity and thickness of the polymer membrane, respectively; it should be noted that the conductivity is calculated moment by moment from a series of equations which, starting from the concentrations of water vapor at the anode and cathode, define how this permeates the membrane and consequently what the actual conductivity value is.

Finally, as shown in Figure5.17, the so-called Double Layer Effect is also considered by means of a capacitor. This results in a dynamic response of the effective voltage.

The equations that define the use of reagents, the power created and dissipated and consequently the efficiency is also modeled in the central block (MEA),

By way of example [4]:

$$H_2_{consumed} = \frac{N_{cell} i_{cell} MM_{H_2}}{2F}, \quad O_2_{consumed} = \frac{N_{cell} i_{cell} MM_{O_2}}{4F}, \quad H_2O_{produced} = \frac{N_{cell} i_{cell} MM_{H_2O_2}}{2F}$$

Furthermore, depending on whether the effect of the condensation of the water produced is considered, two efficiencies are distinguished, one based on the higher calorific value and one on the lower calorific value of hydrogen:

$$LHV_{efficiency} = \frac{V_{cell} 2F}{LHV_{H_2}} \quad HHV_{efficiency} = \frac{V_{cell} 2F}{HHV_{H_2}}$$

Now, by observing the anode side of the cell (Figure5.18), one can see in order:

- **Hydrogen source:** it is essentially a pressurized cylinder connected to a valve. The latter determines the flow rate of hydrogen output and the pressure inside the anode ducts by means of a control that exploits the pressure feedback downstream from the valve.
- **Recirculation:** in this block the "exhausted" hydrogen flows into the "fresh" one so as to avoid wasting fuel and increase efficiency. A control defines the extent of this recirculation.

- *Humidification*: here, by means of a control, the flow rate of water vapor necessary to mix with the hydrogen is defined in such a way as to bring the relative humidity of the mixture to 100%, for a substantial increase in performance.
- *Anode gas channels*: essentially, the ducts that carry the gases up to the gas diffusion layers of the cell are modeled.
- *Anode exhaust*: inside there is a duct that exchanges heat with the environment and a valve that allows gases to escape when necessary.

Figure 5.18. Scheme of components and signals of the anode

As regards the cathode side (Figure 5.19), there are the *Cathode gas Channels* and *Humidification*, in which the same considerations made for the anode apply. Furthermore, the following components are modeled:

- *Oxygen source*: inside, a compressor takes air from the environment and compresses it to the desired pressure. The flow rate is defined through Look Up Tables and a control system that provides the necessary rotation speed. A higher flow rate than necessary is preferred, so as to avoid a lack of oxygen at the cathode.
- *Cathode exhaust*: as with the anode, a valve determines the flow rate expelled into the environment and allows the cathode pressure to be kept equal to the desired one.

Figure 5.19 Scheme of the structure and signals of the cathode

Finally, a *Cooling system* is provided (see Figure 5.165.16). The heat produced by the Fuel Cell and the heat exchanged with the cathode and anode channels converge here. Once the working temperature of the cell has been defined (80°C), a control determines the command for a pump that circulates the cooling liquid, water in this case, responsible for the heat exchange with the environment.

Example of simulation results

A preliminary simulation of the Fuel Cell is proposed, in which all the gas dynamics were not considered, but only the electrical one. So, the inputs in this simulation are hydrogen and air at a pressure of 0.16 MPa with a humidity of 100%. A current ramp was set (up to the value of i_L , limit current) to obtain the I-V characteristic and the power output. Figure 5.20 shows the simulation results.

Figure 5.20. results of simulation of the custom fuel cell

In the first graph we can see how the voltage decreases as the current increases due to losses. In particular, activation losses (light blue line) even show at low currents, and then settle down. The concentration losses (green line) are almost negligible, since they act at high currents, while the ohmic ones (red line) may be relevant and strongly depend on the hydration level of the membrane. The second graph instead shows how the output power density increases as the current

increases, until it reaches values close to the limit current: here the potential drops more quickly due to excessive losses. The results are in line with the one reported by measuring real FC in [1].

References

- [1] B. Gou, W. Na, and B. Diong, *Fuel cells - Dynamic modeling and control with power electronics applications*, Second Edition. CRC Press, 2017.
- [2] Mathworks, "Model PEM fuel cells with Simulink and Simscape," Mathworks. Accessed: Oct. 22, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://it.mathworks.com/discovery/fuel-cell-model.html>
- [3] Mathworks, "Modeling a PEM Fuel Cell," Mathworks. Accessed: Oct. 22, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://it.mathworks.com/videos/modeling-a-pem-fuel-cell-1657875274071.html>
- [4] S. Colleen. *PEM fuel cell modeling and simulation using MATLAB*. Elsevier, 2008.
- [5] P. Jay T., Anna G. Stefanopoulou, and Huei Peng. *Control of fuel cell power systems: principles, modeling, analysis and feedback design*. Springer-Verlag London, 2004.

Task 5.6 Analysis of the state of the art of dynamic gas journal bearings (POLITO-DIMEAS)

In the following a model of herringbone grooved bearings from references [1, 2] is presented. This model is an evolution of the model shown in [3] as the model of Whipple can in certain cases lead to very considerable errors.

Different geometries of grooved bearings are possible, see table below. It is possible to have a null (Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b) or not null (Fig. 1c and Fig. 1d) net flow of air which crosses the bearing in radial direction. The surface of the bearing can be entirely grooved (Fig. 5.21a and Fig. 5.21b) or partially grooved (Fig. 5.21c and Fig. 5.21d). The radial net flow can be along the outward direction (Fig. 5.21c) or the inward direction (Fig. 5.21d); in the first case, the spiral grooves create an outward pumping effect, pumping the air from the internal radius to the center of the bearing; in the second case the pumping is inwardly, as the air is pumped from the outside of the bearing.

Fig. 5.21c: Flat thrust bearing, partially grooved, outward pumping

Fig. 5.21d: Flat thrust bearing, partially grooved, inward pumping

The model of Muijderman

The geometry analysed by Muijderman is depicted in figure 5.22.

Figure 5.22: The geometry analysed by Muijderman.

The following dimensionless quantities are defined:

$$H = \frac{h_2}{h_1}: \text{film height ratio}$$

$$\gamma = a_2/a_1: \text{ridge to groove width ratio}$$

$$\delta = \frac{h_2}{h_0} = \frac{h_2}{h_1 - h_2} = \frac{H}{1-H}: \text{alternative film height ratio}$$

Here are reported just the final expressions of load capacity and maximum pressure of the model described in [1,2], while all passages that demonstrate them can be consulted in the references.

The pressure distribution is assumed to be linear (see Fig. 3) according to

$$\bar{p}_1 = \bar{p}_{10} + A_1 \bar{x} + C_1 \bar{z}$$

$$\bar{p}_2 = \bar{p}_{20} + A_2 \bar{x} + C_2 \bar{z}$$

$$\bar{p}_{1'} = \bar{p}_{1'0} + A_{1'} \bar{x} + C_{1'} \bar{z}$$

$$\bar{p}_{2'} = \bar{p}_{2'0} + A_{2'} \bar{x} + C_{2'} \bar{z}$$

where p_1 is the pressure in the groove and p_2 the pressure in the ridge.

The density is assumed to be constant, which is realistic in case the pressure is not far from ambient pressure.

Figure 5.23: sketch of the pressure distribution

The pressure difference between the edge at $z=0$ and the edge at $z=d$ is

$$\Delta \bar{p} = A_1 \cot \alpha + C_1$$

where coefficients A_1 and C_1 depend on geometry, according to [2].

- [1] Mujiderman, E. A., 1964, "Spiral Groove Bearings," Technological University of Delft, Delft, The Netherlands.
- [2] Mujiderman, E. A., 1967, "Analysis and Design of Spiral-Groove Bearings", J Lubr. Tech., 1967, pp. 291-306.
- [3] R.T.P. Whipple, Theory of the Spiral Grooved Thrust Bearing with Liquid or Gas Lubricant, Technical Report, Great Britain Atomic Energy Research Establishment, Harwell, Berks, England, 1951.

Task 5.7 Development of a numerical model of bearings (POLITO-DIMEAS)

A mathematical model based on [1] has been made in order to estimate the load carrying capacity of a dynamic gas thrust bearing with herringbone pattern. In the next paragraph the geometry will be defined, as well as the output results of the model.

Task 5.7.1: NGT for estimating the load capacity of a gas thrust bearing with herringbone pattern

The geometry

The geometry of the thrust bearing is here below sketched, where the circumference direction is represented by x axis, while the radial direction by y axis. A set of grooves are machined on the thrust surface, inclined of an angle θ with respect to the radial direction. The pressure is assumed to be null (ambient pressure) at the internal radius ($y=b+c$) and the external radius ($y=0$).

The load capacity per unit of circumferential length is given by the integration of the pressure distribution according to

$$T = \int_0^{b+c} (p - p_0) dy \cong \frac{b+c}{2} (P - p_0)$$

where P is the maximum mean pressure, which occurs at y=b.

Different geometries are considered, by varying the following dimensionless parameters:

$$X = \frac{a_1}{a_2}$$

$$Y = \frac{r_3 - r_2}{r_3 - r_1} = \frac{b}{b+c}$$

For each geometry, ratio P/p₀ and T are calculated. The goal is to find the optimal geometry of the thrust bearing which maximizes the load capacity. For these calculations, the air gap in the groove was considered to be h₁=8 μm, while in the ridge h₂=5 μm. Another parameter that was changed is the number of grooves N.

The sensitivity analysis

The following reference geometry is considered for the sensitive analysis:

N=12, X=0.7, Y=0.4, r₁/r₃=0.5, teta=30°

Starting from this reference geometry, each parameter was changed to evaluate the effect on the pressure distribution and the load capacity.

Variation of Y

N=12, X=0.7, r ₁ /r ₃ =0.5, teta=30°		
Y=0.2	Y=0.4	Y=0.6
P/p ₀ = 1.49 ; T=246 N/m	P/p ₀ = 1.79 ; T=395 N/m	P/p ₀ = 1.85 ; T=429 N/m

If parameter Y is changed from Y=0.2 to Y=0.6 both P and T increase.

Variation of X

N=12, Y=0.4, r ₁ /r ₃ =0.5, teta=30°
--

X=0.7	X=1	X=1.5
$P/p_0 = 1.79$; $T = 395$ N/m	$P/p_0 = 1.82$; $T = 414$ N/m	$P/p_0 = 1.82$; $T = 413$ N/m

If parameter X is changed from X=0.7 to X=1.5 both P and T initially increase but then reach a maximum.

Variation of N

X=1, Y=0.4, $r_1/r_3=0.5$, $\text{teta}=30^\circ$		
N=8	N=12	N=20
$P/p_0 = 1.83$; $T = 414$ N/m	$P/p_0 = 1.82$; $T = 414$ N/m	$P/p_0 = 1.83$; $T = 414$ N/m

As visible from the table above, in this model the number of grooves does not influence the maximum mean pressure P and the load capacity T .

Variation of ratio r_1/r_3

N=12, X=1, Y=0.4, $\text{teta}=30^\circ$		
$r_1/r_3=0.3$	$r_1/r_3=0.5$	$r_1/r_3=0.7$
$P/p_0 = 2.1$; $T = 776$ N/m	$P/p_0 = 1.82$; $T = 414$ N/m	$P/p_0 = 1.52$; $T = 156$ N/m

In case ratio r_1/r_3 is increased, both P and T decrease.

Change of angle θ

N=12, X=1, Y=0.4, r1/r3=0.5		
$\theta=30^\circ$	$\theta=45^\circ$	$\theta=70^\circ$
P/p ₀ = 1.83 ; T=414 N/m	P/p ₀ = 2.04; T=520 N/m	P/p ₀ = 1.77 ; T=384 N/m

Such results show that the optimal angle is about 45° .

The non-linear optimization

Given the values of h_1 and h_2 and fixed a rotational speed $\omega=100$ krpm, a non-linear algorithm is employed to find the solution that maximizes the load capacity T.

$h_1=8e-6$; %air gap in the groove
 $h_2=5e-6$; %air gap in the ridge
 $r_1/r_3=0.5$

In the following table, the optimal parameters X, Y and θ are shown in case N=12 and N=8. Of course the solution is the same, as N does not influence the load capacity in this model, but the geometries look different.

<p>N=12: X: 1.2989 Y: 0.5594 teta: 49.1026 T=584.6235 N/m</p>	<p>N=8: X: 1.2989 Y: 0.5594 teta: 49.1026 T= 584.6243 N/m</p>
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[1] R.T.P. Whipple, Theory of the Spiral Grooved Thrust Bearing with Liquid or Gas Lubricant, Technical Report, Great Britain Atomic Energy Research Establishment, Harwell, Berks, England, 1951.

Task 5.8 Realization of a demonstrator (POLITO-DIMEAS)

The first concept of the demonstrator is here depicted. In the section are visible the journal bearings, of herringbone type, the thrust bearing, of spiral groove type, the electric motor and the compressor disk which emulates a real radial compressor from a rotodynamic point of view, having the same mass and moment of inertia.

Both the thrust bearing and the journal bearings will be designed to support the shaft up to 200 krpm, showing the feasibility of supporting the shaft of a real radial compressor.

The next steps will be about:

- Definition of the size of the compressor
- Estimation of the required load capacity of the thrust bearing
- Design of journal bearings
- Design of the thrust bearing

Output and results:

In this reporting period Nafion membranes have been prepared using green solvents selected in the first semester. The membranes produced have been compared with commercial samples produced with traditional approaches. Development of GDE for PEM fuel cells.

Experimental activities focused on testing new deposition technologies functional to the elimination of solvent-based primers and adhesives from processes.

Experimental activity started, to test LIG-nanostructured electrodes as an innovative and low-cost catalyst capable of replacing platinum.

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

No equipments

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

- Nafion membranes prepared with selected solvents will be characterized in terms of proton conductivity as a function of the temperature and relative humidity.
- Based on the results the preparation protocol of the polymeric membrane will be optimized.
- Mixed matrix membranes in which an organic and an inorganic phase coexist in synergic way, will be also developed.
- Strengthening the analysis of LIG-S co-catalytic behavior.
- Exploring decoration of different LIG substrates with Pt/free catalysts

- Expanding simulation of the Fuel Cell for application to boats
- Extending the use of GDE systems for half-cell analysis exploring different MEA preparation methods
- Extending models and analysis for the development of the demonstrator

Key Indicators for Research activities and Flagship Projects:

Action	Key Indicator	Flagship overall target	Flagship progress
Outcome	Number of Pilot Line / Demonstrators / Prototypes	2	0
	Number of publications	20 journal papers /publications in international conferences	3
	Number of registered IPR (patents, utility models, trademarks, industrial designs)	2	0
Output	Number of professor and researcher involved	16	21
	Personnel effort dedicated to Research and Innovation and Flagship Project (person/month in three years)	146,5 PM	25,53

2. IMPACT

TESTO del 1° REPORT:

This phase of the project has been useful to consolidate the management structure of the FP and the coordination of the different actors involved. The research activities have been fully identified and the research activities set up. Preliminary results have been obtained, but not yet sufficiently mature, so that the number of outcomes and products is still limited.

One publication, one conference proceedings and one conference presentation are available.

No IPR has been produced yet.

3. INDUSTRY PARTICIPATION AND INNOVATIONS (prototypes, clinical trials, Testing activities etc.)

In this reporting period the contents of the Flagship have been presented in different meetings with companies during the events for the launch of cascade calls dedicated to the South. Indeed CNR-ITM participated to the event dedicated to the presentation of Spoke 1 financing opportunities for companies in the South held at the Polytechnic of Bari on June 22nd 2023.

All the researchers involved in the FP are intensifying their research relationships with companies. To this end, they are establishing relationships with new companies and to identify topics of real interest where researchers' expertise may be of interest.

4. FOLLOW-UP OF RECOMMENDATIONS AND COMMENTS FROM PREVIOUS REVIEW(S) (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable

5. OPEN SCIENCE PRACTISES AND UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable

6. RESULTS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

This phase of the project has been useful to consolidate the management structure of the FP and the coordination of the different actors involved. The research activities have been fully identified and the research activities set up. Up to now only preliminary results have been obtained.

Add actual delivery dates (or new due date for late deliverables, together with an explanation for the delay). In the Comments, please indicate if the deliverable was achieved as planned or not.

The labels used mean:

Public — fully open; Sensitive — limited; R — Restricted; C — Confidential; S — Secret.

D. No	Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Status	Comments
[number]	[name]	[RM Number]	[short name]	[R — Document, report] [DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA — data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP — Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]	[PU — Public] [SEN — Sensitive] [R] [C] [S]	[month number]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[Pending] [Draft] [Submitted] ([Rejected] [Approved] [Removed])	[insert comments]
D1	H2Mobility Report 1	ALL	POLITO	R	PU	12				
D2	H2Mobility Report 2	ALL	POLITO	R	PU	24				
D3	H2Mobility Report 3	RM2 RM5	POLITO	DEM	PU	30				
D4	H2Mobility Report 4	ALL	POLITO	R	PU	36				

Table 1: Deliverables

LIST OF MILESTONES

Milestone No	Milestone Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Achieved	Comments
[number]	[name]	[RM number]	[beneficiary short name]	[means of verification as in Annex 1]	[Month]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[YES] [NO]	[insert comment]
MS1	Milestone 1	ALL	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D1	M12				
MS2	Milestone 2	ALL	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D2	M24				
MS3	Milestone 3	RM2 RM5	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D3	M30				
MS4	Milestone 4	ALL	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D4	M36				

Table 2: Milestones

LIST OF CRITICAL RISKS

State of play: Give the state of play of the risks that were identified (and new risks that materialised during project implementation) and add new mitigation measures, if needed.

Risk No	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?	Did your risk materialize?	Comments
[risk number]	[YES] [NO]	[YES] [NO]	[insert comment (mandatory if no risk mitigation measures were applied or planned risk mitigation measures were not applied)]

Table 3: Risks

PROJECT PATHWAY TO IMPACT

Provide details about the project results. Please focus on the content of the results, for example discoveries and theories,

products, services, methods etc. Publications, intellectual property rights, datasets, software, algorithms, protocols etc. will be linked to these results later in separate tables. It will also be possible to add these to the project as a whole.

Examples:

- The project developed a new medical device, which is described in two publications and later patented. Instructions: List the medical device here (as 'PROD: Product') and add publications to this product in dedicated sections. When you have information about the patent application, add it in a dedicated section.
- The project developed a new scientific theory which is described in several publications. Instructions: List the name and potential of the theory here (as 'SCI: Scientific discovery, model, theory') and add relevant publications later in dedicated sections.
- The project develops a high potential industrial process and is currently at the stage of prototyping. Instructions: List the industrial process here (as 'PROC: Industrial process') and indicate the prototyping stage under 'Steps undertaken towards exploitation'. If there is a registered prototype, add the registered prototype in a dedicated section.

Name	Result type	TRLs	Steps undertaken towards exploitation (multiple choice)	Market maturity (state of the market targeted by this result)
[name]	[SCI — Scientific discovery, model, theory...] [PROD — Product (new or improved)] [SERV — Service (new or improved)] [PROC — Industrial process (new or improved)] [BUS — Business model (new or improved)] [DSG — Design (new or improved)] [METH — Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)] [PO — Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy] [EVNT — Event (conference, seminar, workshop)] [STAFF — (qualified personnel exchanges)] [LEARN — learning and training (learning modules, curricula)] [INFRA — new or improved infrastructures or facilities]	[TRL1- Basic principles observed] [TRL2- Technology concept validated] [TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept] [TRL4 - Technology validated in lab] [TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment] [TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment] [TRL8- System complete and qualified] [TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment] [Not applicable]	[Prototyping in laboratory environment] [Prototyping in production environment] [Pilot, demonstration or testing] [Intellectual property management] [Complying with regulatory framework] [Contribution to standards] [Feasibility Study] [Market Study] [Business plan] [Other]	[Not yet existing and not clear if market can be created] [Market creating: not existing but potential for the creation of a new market] [Emerging: growing demand, scarce supply] [Mature: the market is already supplied with similar products]
CNR_	EVNT (Roma, 18-22 September 2023)	[Not applicable]	[Not applicable]	[Not applicable]

Participation to Conference				
CNR _ Presentation to Spoke 1 financing opportunities for companies in the South	EVNT (Polytechnic of Bari, June 22 nd 2023)	TRL 6 - 7	[Not applicable]	[Not applicable]

Table 4: Results

PUBLICATIONS

Type of publication	Peer - review	Type of PID (repositor y)	PID of deposited publication	Link to publication (if no PID of publication)	Title of the publication (for book chapters: title of chapter not of book)	ISSN/ eSSN (if book insert ISBN)	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number	Publisher	Month/ Year of publication	Book title (if book chapter)	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	License type
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[Article in journal] [Publication in conference proceeding/ Workshop] [Book/Monograph] [Chapter in book] [Thesis/Dissertation] [Other]	[YES] [NO]	[DOI] [handle] [ARK] [URI] [pURL] [Other] [None]	[insert PID reference]	[insert link]	[insert title of publication]	[insert ISSN/eISSN number]	[insert author names]	[insert title of journal]	[insert number of journal]	[insert name of publisher]	[insert month of publication] [insert year of publication]	[insert book title]	[YES] [NO]	[CC BY or equivalent] [CC BY NC or equivalent] [CC BY NC ND or equivalent] [Other licences]
Conference	NO	[None]	[None]	https://www.nanoinnovation2023.eu/home/index.php/programme/workshops/ws-ii-sustainable-technologies	Development of proton exchange membranes using green solvents		E. Fontananova	NanoInnovation 2023	Workshop II: "Emerging materials and technologies for a sustainable society"					
Article in journal	YES	10.1016/j.cattod.2023.01.030			CO2 hydrogenation to methanol over Zr- and	9205861	Salomone F., Sartoretti E., Ballauri S., Castellino M., Novara C., Giorgis F.,	Catalysis Today	423	Elsevier	2023			

					Ce-doped indium oxide		Pirone R., Bensaid S.							
Publication in conference proceeding			https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-32439-0_35	Gas Bearings Applications in Automotive Fuel Cell Technology.		Colombo, F., Lentini, L., Raparelli, T., Trivella, A.	Proceedings of I4SDG Workshop 2023. I4SDG 2023. Petuya, V., Quaglia, G., Parikyan, T., Carbone, G.	134	Springer, Cham.	2023				

Table 5: Publications

DATASETS

Short Name:	
Description of datasets:	
Data origin:	

Data type:	
Data Formats:	
Useful for whom:	
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	<i>[N/A] [open access given to data] [[other: please describe]]</i>
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	<i>Persistent identifier and project metadata (provision of metadata and documentation) - URL to repository</i>
Accessibility:	<i>[Fully open à repository] [Partially open à repository and access methods] [no à motivation]</i>
Interoperability:	<i>Standards for interoperability</i>
Reusability:	<i>Licensing and restrictions, repository for long term preservation [CCBY or equivalent] [CCO or equivalent to CCO] [Other]</i>
Open	<i>[YES][Partially][NO] - Access methods</i>

Table 6: Data sets

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPRs)

Type of IP Rights	Application Title	Application Reference	Application Date	IPR Owner	IPR Status Has protection been awarded?	IPR Award Reference ID
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[Software] [Workflow] [Protocol] [Prototype] [Other]	[insert description]	[N/A] [open access given to data] [[other: please describe]]	Expected by Project 'end: [TRL1- Basic principles observed] [TRL2- Technology concept validated] [TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept] [TRL4 - Technology validated in lab] [TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment] [TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment] [TRL8- System complete and qualified] [TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment] [Not applicable]	[DOI] [handle] [ARK] [URI] [Other]	[insert PID reference]	[insert URL]	[CCBY or equivalent] [CC0 or equivalent to CC0] [Other]

Table 8: Other results

IMPACT in terms of TRLs, SDGs, KSOs

(in blue the selection applicable for the Flagship)

Technology readiness level of the project	
At project' start: [an item.]	Expected by Project 'end:
RM1 _ TRL 4	[TRL1- Basic principles observed]
RM2 _ TRL 4	[TRL2- Technology concept validated]
RM3 _ TRL 4	[TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept]
RM4 _ TRL 4	[TRL4 - Technology validated in lab]
RM5 _ TRL 4	[TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment]
Current status: [an item.]	[TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment]
No change	[TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment]
	[TRL8- System complete and qualified]
	[TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment]
	[Not applicable]

Table 9: TRLs

Is your project likely to deliver results relevant for the following Sustainable Development Goals?	
Climate neutrality	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Clean Water and Sanitation	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Life Below Water	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Life on Land	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
No Poverty	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Zero Hunger	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant]
	[Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Good Health and Well-being	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Gender Equality	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Decent Work and Economic Growth	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Affordable and Clean Energy	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]

Reduced Inequality	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Sustainable Cities and Communities	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Responsible Consumption and Production	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Quality Education	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Peace and Justice Strong Institutions	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
International cooperation	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Please explain your choice:	[insert text]

Table 10: SDGs

Horizon Europe KEY STRATEGIC ORIENTATIONS (KSO)	Horizon Europe Impact Areas	Contribution to the KSO and the relevant expected impacts
KSO 1 Promoting an open strategic autonomy by leading the development of key digital and enabling technologies, sectors and value chains to accelerate and steer the digital and green transitions through human-centred technologies and innovations	A competitive and secure data-economy	
	Industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people	
	Secure and cyber-secured digital technology	
	High quality digital services for all	
KSO 2 Restoring Europe's ecosystems and biodiversity, and managing sustainably natural resources to ensure food security and a clean and healthy environment	Enhancing ecosystems and biodiversity on land and in waters	
	Clean and healthy air, water and soil	
	Sustainable food systems and nutrition security	
KSO 3 Making Europe the first digitally led circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy through the transformation of its mobility, energy, construction and production	Climate change mitigation and adaptation	
	Affordable and clean energy	
	Smart and sustainable transport	

systems	Circular and clean economy	
KSO 4 Creating a more resilient, inclusive and democratic European society , prepared and responsive to threats and disasters, addressing inequalities and providing high-quality health	A resilient EU prepared for emerging threats	

Table 11: KSOs and Impact Areas - HE